

An Intelligent Trust Evaluation for Business-To-Business
Electronic Commerce Using HyperTernary Model

BY

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Philosophy in Computer Science.

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DECLARATION

I hereby declare that this Thesis was written by me and is a correct record of my own research work. It has not been presented in any previous application for any degree of this or any other University. All citations and sources of information are clearly acknowledged by means of references.

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CERTIFICATION

We certify that this Thesis entitled “An Intelligent Trust Evaluation for Business-To-Business Electronic Commerce Using HyperTernary Model” is the outcome of the research carried out by Ayodeji Samuel Makinde in the Department of Computer Science, Federal University of Agriculture, Abeokuta.

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ABSTRACT

The issue of trust is significant in Business-to-Business (B2B) e-commerce because it exists between two groups of transacting partners. However, B2B trust is associated with some challenges, which include inconsistency in purchase decision-making, complexity in customer relationship management, risk of customer churning and switching costs. Buyer Collective Process (BCP), Feedback-Based Diagnosis System (FBDS), Fuzzy Analytic Hierarchy Process (Fuzzy-AHP), Path model, Relational Unified (RU) model, Support Vector Machine (SVM), K-means, C5.0 and Dynamic Time Decay (DTD) are the dominant models used for tackling these challenges. This study presents an intelligent trust evaluation for B2B e-commerce using a HyperTernary (HT) model to address some of the challenges. The HT model was made up of three different modules: Customer Relationship Management (CRM), Customer Satisfaction and Retention (CSR), and Purchase Decision-making (PDM) modules. Adaptive Network-based Fuzzy Inference System (ANFIS) was adopted to validate customer satisfaction and retention, while Analytic Hierarchical Process and Multilayer Perceptron Neural Network (Analytic-MLP) was used for the customer PDM. This work was implemented with Python programming language and MyStructured Query Language (MySQL) using two B2B e-commerce scenarios, which were Publishers versus Library team interaction and building material manufacturer versus suppliers. Primary data were collected through questionnaires administered online to B2B e-commerce experts. The secondary data were collected from online B2B e-commerce websites. The experiments were evaluated using accuracy, precision, computational time and consistency. Results showed that the proposed model had an accuracy of 98.3% with a computational time of 6.47ms for CRM as compared with SVM, K-means, and C5.0 with

93.21, 90.6 and 78.1% accuracies and 7.11, 6.95 and 6.52ms computational times respectively. In addition, the HT model showed high accuracy and precision level of 98.7 and 58% for CSR as compared with DTD, Path model and RU model, which have accuracy and precision level of (90.2 and 47%); (94.6 and 53%); and (88 and 43%) respectively. High computational time was detected in ANFIS with 8.21ms compared with DTD, Path model and RU model which had 8.09, 8.13 and 7.98ms respectively. The high computational time was as a result of the Gaussian membership function used to achieve high accuracy. Analytic-MLP of the HT model showed high performance in accuracy and computational time with 97.80% and 7.35ms respectively for customer purchase decision making. The corresponding accuracies and computational times for BCP, FBDS, and Fuzzy-AHP were 89.30, 8.16; 94.61, 11.47; and 95.98%, and 8.39ms respectively. The consistency level was measured using congruence (ψ) and dissonance (Θ) measurement with 0.083 and 0.905 compared with 0.057 and 0.821 of Fuzzy-AHP model respectively. The HT performed better than other models both in accuracy and computational time, ensuring high consistency in buyers' opinions, thereby improving customer relationship and reducing churning. Arising from these results, the model provided a trusted B2B e-commerce interactions for purchase decision-making, customer relationship management, and customer satisfaction and retention.

DEDICATION

This Thesis is dedicated to God Almighty whom through His Word encouraged me and has been a driving force that kept me moving, strong and determined.

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CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 BACKGROUND

Electronic commerce (E-commerce) also refers to as internet commerce is the buying and selling of goods or services using the internet, and the transfer of money and data to execute these transactions (Burt and Sparks, 2003). E-commerce is crucial to the developed countries because it contributes by bringing great transformation to the country. E-commerce has bridged the barrier of time, space, nationality, by catalysing trade patterns and ameliorating the exposure of capital, product and transaction information (Qin, 2010). E-commerce is a new economic revolution based on digitisation and the internet. It represents a significant reduction in the cost of production (Zheng et al., 2009). It has set enterprises to have the edge over others because it allows easy reachability of new customers, which gives rooms for automated cross-sell and up-sell recommendation systems (Korpela, 1996). Thus, the organisation could meet market demands; customer needs and thereby reaching forth to new customers (Youcef, 2004; Chen *et al.*, 2008; Chen and Xiao-Liang, 2015; Jun-Chen, 2015).

Different types of e-commerce have been established based on their nature of market relationship. The most common is the Business-to-Consumer (B2C) process, which creates electronic storefronts that offer information, goods and services between business and consumers in a retailing transaction (Nanehkaran, 2013). B2C is an e-commerce transaction between a business and an end consumer. The second type of e-commerce is the Consumer-to-Consumer (C2C), which provides opportunities for consumers to sell to

each other, with the help of online market makers such as auction site, for instance, eBay, JiJi and Amazon. In C2C e-commerce, the consumer prepares the products for the market, places the product for auction and relies on the market maker to provide a catalogue, search engine and transaction-clearing capabilities so that products can be easily displayed, discovered and purchase (Laudon and Traver, 2013).

In Business-to-Government (B2G) e-commerce, is a business model that refers to businesses selling products, services or information to government agencies. Government as national administrator plays a significant role in guiding, administering and adjusting the economy. B2G e-commerce provide a way for businesses to bid on government projects or products that governments might purchase for their organizations.

Business-to-Business (B2B) e-commerce is an internet business model that involves businesses that perform services or provide products for other businesses. B2B renders the best platform for the organisation to launch a comprehensive analytics advert, thereby having positive significant saving potential and it is easily validated (Canavari *et al.*, 2010; Campanella *et al.*, 2011; Grewal *et al.*, 2015).

Trust is an enabler that lets customers' undertake a potentially risky operation even though it is potentially risky. Trust determines the conditions for allowing a particular action. Trust is an important element of any e-commerce society, critical to the moral cohesion of a community. Without trust in any institutions, a society cannot survive. Trust is also an essential element of trade relations (Hofstede *et al.*, 2010). From a utilitarian point of view, trust saves money. Trusting a trade partner reduces perception of transaction risks and saves

the cost of control. Psychologically, people are driven to search for and to maintain trusting relationships.

An Intelligent System (IS) is a system with an embedded, internet-connected computer that has the capacity to gather and analyze data and communicate with other systems. IS has the capacity to learn from experience, connectivity, the ability to adapt according to current data and the capacity for remote monitoring and management.

Transaction in B2B e-commerce involves a larger volume of data; hence, building and maintaining customer relationships through online activities to facilitate the exchange of ideas, products, and services that satisfy the goals of both parties is a problem (Afef Denguir-Rekik, 2009; Brown *et al.*, 2011). Understanding and responding to customers' needs, attitude, and behaviour towards a product have always been a pillar of the marketing strategy. Therefore, it is necessary to invest in knowing and understanding the customer decision-making strategies, in order for B2B e-commerce to gain competitive advantage (Thatcher *et al.*, 2006; Amelinckx *et al.*, 2008; Wiersema, 2013; Gordini, 2017). B2B is vital in e-commerce because of its volume of business, lower operation cost, suitable for modern logistics management, competitive in guaranteeing credit and capital security during operation course, and its maturity in both theory and practice (Wind and Robert, 2010; Kamiri, 2013; Grawal *et al.*, 2015).

This study focuses on B2B e-commerce because of its importance to researchers and practitioners. Despite the failure of hundreds of B2B exchanges since the dot.com crash in early 2000, businesses are plunging ahead with B2B e-commerce (Teo and Ranganathan, 2004; Ng, 2005). International B2B alliances have become critical components for creating

more significant value to meet customer expectations and subsequently, achieving a firm's intended growth and performance objectives. Former research suggested that trust in Internet-based B2B e-commerce is an essential factor for both practitioners and academicians alike.

1.2 MOTIVATION

The major motivation for this study hinges on B2B Purchase Decision-Making (PDM), Customer Satisfaction and Retention (CSR), and Customer Relationship Management (CRM). The nature of B2B markets indicates that consumer tastes and preferences vary dramatically across borders and cultures, but a primary driver of transactions in B2B markets derived demand and holds everywhere. The B2B marketplace matches up well with the increasingly global academic market, which means that multinational research partnerships have the potential to bring more efficiency to B2B research than to B2C research.

Customer churn and switching cost are critical factors that should not be ignored by B2B e-commerce companies. Customer churn indicates the propensity of customers to cease doing business with a company in a given period (Verbeke et al., 2011). Due to improved access to information, customers are more transient, and it is more comfortable and less costly for them to switch between competitors (Tamaddoni et al., 2014, 2016; Wiersema, 2013).

In order to perfect CSR, CRM needs to be considered. CRM is an art of building individual relationships with high-value customers to enjoy their continued patronage and archiving a win-win outcome for both the seller and customers (Soltani and Navimipour 2016). CRM

technique allows businesses to organise, automate and synchronise every area of customer interaction (Jafari and Soltani 2016). CRM creates loyal customers and increase sellers profit regardless of economic condition and allow the customers to receive quality products and services. CRM technique in B2B e-commerce setting involved seller managing different customers with different perceptives but working towards the same goal (Gunasekaran et al., 2002; Soltani and Navimipour, 2016)

1.3 PROBLEM STATEMENT

The problem statement considered in this study are as follows:

1.3.1 Complexity and inconsistency in B2B PDM

Purchase Decision-Making (PDM) process in B2B e-commerce is complicated and frequently characterised by conflicting situations. Purchasing decision is rarely made independently without the influence of other stakeholders (Grawal et al., 2015). Unlike B2C where buying is often a standalone and primarily requiring little or no follow-up, in B2B, buying decision is full of emotions and fear of who will accommodate decision's flexibility. In addition, B2B buying may involve at least two groups of individuals with different backgrounds and incentives in the buying process (Lilien, 2016). Consequently, buying decisions at the organisational levels are rendered complex due to the diversities in decision makers' judgments with inconsistencies experienced in buyers' opinions (Gordini and Veglio, 2017).

1.3.2 Customer Churn

Customer churn is a salient concept in contemporary marketing and should not be ignored by B2B e-commerce companies. Customer churn indicates the propensity of customers to

cease doing business with a company in a given period (Tamaddoni et al., 2014; Verbeke et al., 2011). Due to improved access to information, customers are more transient, and it is easier and less costly for them to switch between competitors (Tamaddoni et al., 2016; Wiersema, 2013). Companies are aware of this and are interested in identifying potential churners in order to attempt to prevent defection by targeting such customers with incentives. Therefore, with the purpose of retaining and satisfying customers, it is crucial to building a trust prediction model that is as accurate as possible in order to minimise the customer risk of churn (Gordini and Veglio, 2017).

1.3.3 Customer group variation

Online purchase processes are designed through the interactions of consumers with the internet. Therefore, consumers' group characteristics are among the main factors that influence the PDM process (Hosseini and Mohammad, 2016). However, factors that influence customer behaviour, includes social, economic, individual characteristics and cultural.

1.3.4 Trust of a group of individuals

One of the reasons that many B2B exchanges fail in today markets is the lack of enough trust coordination between the buyers and suppliers participating in B2B e-marketplaces (Lilien, 2016). Another issue in B2B is information management, which explains what information fields or information elements are shared across the competitors, and what information fields are private. As a result of this, building and maintaining customer relationships through online activities to facilitate the exchange of ideas, products, and services that satisfy the goals of both parties are the major problem in B2B e-commerce.

1.4 OBJECTIVES

The objectives of this thesis are to:

1. Analyse B2B e-commerce decision-making and trust evaluation models.
2. Design an adaptive fuzzy-based scheme for customer purchase decision-making using Analytic-MLP.
3. Design novel model for customer relationship management using Genetic Data Mining.
4. Design a novel model for customer satisfaction and retention using Sugeno-ANFIS.
5. Implement and evaluate the proposed model in (2) to (4) by comparing with existing ones.

1.5 THESIS ORGANISATION

The organisation of the thesis is as follow:

Chapter 2: In this chapter, we introduce different purchase decision-making, trust modelling, and customer relationship management approaches in the B2B e-commerce.

Chapter 3: Chapter three explains the multi-level mixed method research design. The reason for choosing this specific method is justified. The way experiments are conducted, and methods of analysis are described in detail.

Chapter 4: Chapter four presents the implementation and results. It explained the implementation procedure and how different proposed models analysed and compared with other related models.

Chapter 5: The summary, contributions and future work were discussed.

1.6 DEFINITION OF TERMS

Trust: Use to evaluate customer satisfaction and retention in a business organisation. In the course of this study trust evaluation can be referred to as ‘customer satisfaction and retention’.

Consumer/ Customer: This is an individual that purchase products/goods and services

Shop-and-go customer: This is a customer that has no significant impact on the organisation income/profit.

Repeat customer: Potential customer to an organisation during customer relationship management. This is a customer that add to the financial growth of an organization.

Cross-sell: this is an act of encouraging customers to purchase a comparable higher-end product than the one in question.

Up-sell: This is a way of inviting customers to buy related or complementary products.

Satisfaction: It is a measure of how products and services supplied by a company meet or surpass customer expectation in a convenient way that makes the customer loyal to the firm.

Retention: This is an action taken by organisation to reduce number of customer defections.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter aims to put the research problem into consideration by reviewing the related work and explaining the current understanding of trust evaluation in customer satisfaction and retention, CRM, and online organisational PDM. In the first section of the chapter, fundamental concepts of consumer behaviour, in particular decision-making, trust level evaluation and CRM processes were presented. The evolution of these theories over the years was discussed. As part of the objectives of this study is to explore the impact of online consumer behaviour and variations in the behaviour of consumers, some consumer factors were discussed.

The chapter identifies the gaps based on the understanding of B2B online PDM, consumer trust evaluation, and CRM. Furthermore, it discusses the need for new approaches in consumer behaviour towards the stated objectives. Exploring the actual behaviour of consumers towards PDM, trust evaluation, and CRM are discussed. Figure 1 shows the underlying areas of this research.

Figure 1: Underlying Areas of this Research

2.2 B2B E-COMMERCE

B2B e-commerce encompasses the online through an online sales portal, sale of products and services occurs between companies. B2B transactions are much more complex and the transactions prices are highly variable, relying on a number of pricing variable throughout the transaction process. In B2B, business are much larger entities than individual consumers, therefore, the volume of products and services are much higher and have complicated purchase decision making. The complexity of the B2B e-commerce market makes the solution requirements and implementation processes very demanding.

Figure 2 depicts the general process of a B2B e-commerce. This described the relationship that occurs with the company on the side of supplier and another business company on the customer side. This business company could be represented by sole trader, company, or institution. B2B market includes huge number of transactions, and is usually more complex. The complexity leans on number of number of people responsible for the transaction and number of steps in these transactions. As a results, most B2B models are moving away from legacy Electronic Data Interchange (EDI) systems which are expensive and cumbersome to handle to affordable online platforms where buyers and sellers can meet from any part of the world.

Figure 2: General B2B E-Commerce

2.3 OVERVIEW OF CONSUMER BEHAVIOUR

As customers behave differently, the model for PDM, vendor trust level evaluation, and CRM are adapted in different ways by different customers. Over the years, customers have developed mental shortcuts providing a systematic approach to choose among alternatives. However, different people, no matter how similar they are, make a different purchasing decision. This section explained some of the factors affecting customers' behaviour from previous literature.

2.3.1 Factors Affecting Customer Behaviour

As mentioned earlier, consumer behaviour is influenced by many factors, which including situational factors, personal factors, psychological factors, and societal factors.

(i) Situational Factor

Situational influences are temporary conditions that affect how buyers behave. They include physical factors such as attractive store's design and layout when designing the e-commerce website. Suggesting frequently go-with product whenever a customer is making a purchase decision, for instance, bread and milk are frequently purchased together. The assist customer who have no idea of what to purchase online. The time of the day, time of year, and how much time consumers feel like shopping significantly affect their purchase decision. Researchers have discovered whether someone is a "morning shopper" or "evening shopper" affects shopping patterns. Also, the reason for online shopping dramatically affects the amount of time the customer spends on the vendor website. Is the customer making an emergency purchase? Is the customer shopping for a special occasion or gift? Is the customer purchasing something to complete a project and need it quickly?

Customer mood is another situational factor that affects customer behaviour. Sometime customer might feel like shopping and sometimes not.

(ii) Personal Factors

Personality describes a person's disposition, helps show why people are different with their unique traits. The five dominant personality traits frequently discuss by psychologists include openness, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness, and neuroticism. While demographic variables such as income, education, and marital status are important factors influencing consumer behaviour. Consumer lifestyle is another personal factor that influences consumer behaviour.

(iii) Psychological Factors

Motivation is the inward drive that helps in getting what we need. According to Abraham Maslow, an American psychologist developed the hierarchy of needs shown in Figure 3. Consumer perception towards a particular product or the e-commerce as a whole is another subset of psychological factor. It deals with how the consumer interprets the world around him/her and make sense out of it. This can be carried out through an online review of any e-commerce site. Also learning as a significant influence on consumer behaviour, this deals with changing the behaviour of the consumer after gaining more information and experience about the e-commerce site. Learning is the reason why consumer does not purchase the buy product twice. Learning does not just influence what a customer purchase; it influences how they shop. People with limited experience with a product or brand generally seek out more information than people who have used a product before. Besides, attitudes are mental positions or emotional feelings, favourable or unfavourable

evaluations, and action tendencies people have about products, services, companies, ideas, issues, or institutions. Attitudes tend to be enduring and hard to change because they are based on people's values and beliefs.

Figure 3: Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs (McLeod, 2007)

(iv) Societal Factors

Situational factors, personal factors, and psychological factors influence what consumer purchase, but only on a temporary basis. However, societal factors are more outward and have significant influences on consumers' beliefs and the way they make a decision. Culture, one of the societal factors refers to the shared beliefs, customs, behaviours, and attitudes that characterise a society. Culture has been classified as a handed down way of life and is often considered the broadest influence on consumer's behaviour. To some degree, consumers in the same social class exhibit similar purchasing behaviour.

2.4 CUSTOMER RETENTION AND SATISFACTION

2.4.1 Background to Customer Retention and Satisfaction

Switching cost is a new trending issue in the world of e-commerce due to its impact on business growth as well as its necessity for customer retention. The choice of retaining a customer by setting lower prices to new customers to capture market share and higher prices to current locked in customers is affected by switching cost (Cabral, 2016; Ghazali et al., 2016). The customer switching costs give vendors a degree of market power over their repeat-customers (Blut et al., 2016; Shukla et al., 2016). For example, in B2B e-commerce, customers who have previously purchased from one vendor have costs of switching to a competitor's product, even when the two vendors' products and services are functionally identical (El-Manstrly, 2016; Jaroensrisomboon, 2018). The most apparent effect of switching costs is to give vendors some market power over their existing customers, and thus to create the potential for monopoly profits (Russo et al., 2017; Lam et al., 2017).

Recent researches suggest that trust is an essential factor to consider for customer retention (Alsaad et al., 2017; Oliveira et al., 2017; Hansen et al., 2018). Trust has a profoundly positive significant on customer retention and satisfaction; and it is considered as a leading factor in determining customer retention (Sun et al., 2014; Liang et al., 2013; Subramanian et al., 2014; Hussain et al., 2015; Eid, 2015; Han and Hyun, 2015). Trust is viewed in this study as the willingness of a customer to increase his vulnerability to the actions of a vendor whose behaviour he cannot control (Kim et al., 2005; Liu et al., 2013; Seckler et al., 2015; Li et al., 2018). Trust is considered more important in switching cost and customer retention because a trusted vendor would attract more customers no matter the circumstances. Trust can also promote effective customer-care delivery, reduce purchasing costs, and consequently address the issues of switching cost (Carter et al., 2014; Ponte et al., 2015; Ba and Pavlou, 2002; Gefen et al., 2003). Lack of trust in vendor behaviour, especially, the inability to retain and lock-in customers in the face of competition jeopardised customer retention (McKnight et al., 2002; Blut et al., 2015; Matzler et al., 2015; Cabral 2016; Jaroensrisomboon, 2018).

Different methods had been employed to address trust evaluation for customer retention and lock-in. These include Fuzzy Logic (Castro-Schez et al., 2011; Morid and Shajari, 2012; Nilashi and Ibrahim, 2014; Birtolo and Ronca, 2013; Liu et al., 2013, Martinez-Cruz et al., 2015), Artificial Neural Network (Sherchan et al., 2013), Adaptive Network-based Fuzzy Inference System (Abbasimehr and Torokh, 2015; Azadeh et al., 2015; Safa and Ismail, 2014), Mandani Fuzzy System (Al-Qaisi et al., 2015), Path Model (Liu and Zhou, 2010; Oliveira et al., 2017), Dynamic Time Decay (Zhang et al., 2013; Tajeddine et al., 2011), Analytic Hierarchy Process (Singh et al., 2016; Zhang et al., 2012; Li et al., 2013)

and Fuzzy-Analytic Hierarchy Process and Fuzzy Technique for Order Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (Büyüközkan and Çifçi, 2012). Other trust evaluation algorithms include the Belief Theory (BT), Bayesian systems, Fuzzy logic (Chen et al., 2011; Mahalle et al., 2013; Yan et al., 2015), Virtual Communities (Lu et al., 2010) and the Unified Model (Palvia, 2009), Static Weighed Sum, Dynamic Weighted Sum and Regression Analysis (Bao and Chen, 2012; Bao et al., 2013; Chen et al., 2016). However, some of these methods failed to address switching cost and trust as a solution for customer lock-in and retention. Fewer researches on the issue only focused on vendor satisfaction and customer retention (Gordini and Veglio, 2017; Pulles et al., 2016).

This study presents a novel trust model for customer retention with consideration of switching cost using Sugeno-Fuzzy Inference System (Sugeno-FIS) and Adaptive Network-based Fuzzy Inference System (ANFIS) called Sugeno-ANFIS. The fundamentals of trust, which are, competence, integrity, and benevolence (CIB) were considered (Chen and Dhillon, 2003; Gefen et al., 2003; Oliveira et al., 2017). Four trust metrics were used, namely, Customer- Vendor Interaction, Failure Publication, E-commerce Website Update and Security. The model maps all the trust metric parameters to the input membership function (MF), and the input MF were mapped to the rules. The rules were mapped to the set of output parameters and output parameters to output MF. ANFIS was used to automatically optimise the results derived from Sugeno-FIS by adapting it to the parameters of the fuzzy inference system using neural networks.

2.4.2 Related Models to Customer Satisfaction and Retention: Trust Evaluation

Previous researches have proposed models regarding trust in customers' satisfaction and retention in an e-commerce environment. E-commerce trust has taken on very different outcomes in different concepts and at different times (Gordini and Veglio, 2017; Wang, and Emurian, 2005). Trust is a function of time, and it increases as the relationship grows (Gounaris, 2005). Therefore, in defining trust-based evaluation parameters, time and place are key factors (Pulles et al., 2016).

Fuzzy-Analytic Hierarchy Process and Fuzzy-Technique for Order Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (FAHP-TOPSIS) was used for the evaluation of multi-criteria decision making (MCDM). The FAHP was used to calculate the criteria weight, while TOPSIS select the best alternative decision. TOPSIS was based on the concept that the chosen alternatives should be the shortest distance from the positive-ideal solution and farthest from the negative-ideal solution for solving an MCDM problem (Büyüközkan and Çifçi, 2012; Aktan and Tosun, 2013; Junior et al., 2014). TOPSIS can consider a non-limited number of alternatives and criteria in the decision-making process. TOPSIS similar to FAHP presents the problem of ranking reversal, and its use of Euclidean distance does not consider the correlation of attributes. It is difficult to weigh attributes and keep the consistency of judgment, especially with additional attributes (Velasquez and Hester, 2013).

Adaptive Network-based Fuzzy Inference System (ANFIS) can self-organise network structures and tune the parameters of the Sugeno fuzzy system. It uses ANN learning algorithm (numerical power) and fuzzy logic inference (verbal power) to relate the input

and output spaces (Abbasimehr and Torokh, 2015; Azadeh et al., 2015). ANFIS is a hybrid learning algorithm that uses gradient descent and least-squares methods to update antecedent and consequent parameters, respectively (Ozger, 2009). ANFIS select Gaussian for its membership function. Mamdani fuzzy system is a type of fuzzy logic method used in a decision support system. Mamdani system is a universal approximator, capable of approximating any continuous functions to a high degree of accuracy (Özger, 2009). Mamdani distinct uniqueness lies in its ability to use, not only numerical data but also verbal data obtained from human knowledge and experience. However, Mamdani fuzzy has limited capacity for dealing with too detailed information compared to ANN models.

Artificial Neural Network (ANN) has been accepted as a tool for modelling complex nonlinear systems, and are widely used for prediction purposes. ANN can avoid the curse of dimensionality in the sense that the approximation error becomes independent of the dimension of the input space. ANN models based on multilayer perceptron (MLP) can handle larger dimensional input space than polynomial expansions (Sherchan et al., 2013). ANN does not provide information about the relative significance of the various parameters but requires a broad diversity of training for operation. The knowledge acquired during the training of the model is stored implicitly and hence make it hard to come up with a reasonable interpretation of the overall structure of the network. It has a slow convergence speed, less generalising performance, arriving at local minimum and over-fitting (Ansari and Riasi, 2016).

On the other hand, the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) has proven to be very useful in multi-criteria decision-making method that helps the decision maker confronted with a

complex problem with multiple conflicting and subjective criteria (Saaty, 2008). It uses pairwise comparisons, which are used to compare both alternatives concerning the various criteria and estimate criteria weights (Singh et al., 2016; Zhang et al., 2012; Li et al., 2013). AHP allows for a detailed, structured and systematic decomposition of the overall problem into its fundamental components and interdependencies, with a significant degree of flexibility. However, AHP only prioritises requirements, does not draw attention towards success critical factors and their corresponding requirements (Ishizaka and Labib, 2009). Moreover, criteria with a large number of sub-criteria tend to receive more weight than when they are less detailed (Ishizaka and Labib, 2011).

Path model is a trust enhancer technique which has been used by internet vendors to obtain adequate solutions to increase trust. Path model has been used to combine dimensions of consumer trust and the sources of trust, in order for internet vendors to build and win consumer trust to survive and realise financial success (Chen and Dhillon, 2003). Dynamic Time Decay (DTD) model focused on trust fraud phenomenon. The model was able to deter trust fraud by raising its cost and promote the growth of small and medium-sized sellers and improve the authenticity of feedback ratings. The path model was used to measure the three main dimensions of trust: competence, integrity, and benevolence (Oliveira et al., 2017). However, the average trust score has a defined upper limit and will not grow in an unrestricted manner; it will be challenging for sellers to achieve this goal (Zhang et al., 2013).

Other trust evaluation algorithms includes the Belief Theory (BT), Bayesian systems, Fuzzy logic (Chen et al., 2011; Mahalle et al., 2013; Yan et al., 2015), Virtual Communities

(Lu et al., 2010) and Unified Model (Palvia, 2009), Static Weighed Sum, Dynamic Weighted Sum and Regression Analysis (Bao and Chen, 2012; Bao et al., 2013; Chen et al., 2016).

Although, several studies have been done regarding trust evaluation in e-commerce, less has been done towards customer satisfaction and retention (Lilien, 2016). Also, trust has been marked out as one of the significant factors for customer satisfaction and retention, especially when two or more people are involved in a transaction. Therefore a novel model is proposed, which combined a Sugeno fuzzy inference system with adaptive-network-based fuzzy inference system (ANFIS) used for the optimisation process. For the trust evaluation process in e-commerce in this study, Sugeno FIS has been described as being computationally useful and works well with optimisation and adaptive techniques, which makes it attractive in control problems, regarding the dynamic nonlinear situation.

2.4.3 Background to Sugeno-ANFIS

There are two types of fuzzy inference system (FIS): the Mamdani and Sugeno. Mamdani system is intuitive and has widespread acceptance because it is suited for human input (Khosravanian et al., 2016). Sugeno or Takagi-Sugeno-Kang, a method of fuzzy inference was introduced in 1985 (Takagi and Sugeno, 1985). The Sugeno system is a more compact and computationally efficient representation compared to Mamdani system. Due to its high compactiveness and computationally efficient, Sugeno is useful for constructing fuzzy models (Kamboj and Kaur, 2013; Dehnavi et al., 2015). The adaptiveness of the Sugeno allows for customisation of the membership functions, which best models the data (Hajek and Olej, 2014). The Sugeno output is either linear or constant. Some other advantages of

the Sugeno over Mamdani system include it is computationally efficient; it performs optimally with linear techniques, it has guaranteed continuity of the output surface, and well suited for mathematical analysis (dos Reis et al., 2015).

Sugeno is seen as a universal approximator and has better skill in estimating the current value from two antecedent values as compared to ANN. The adaptive techniques like ANFIS can create a fuzzy system that would match any set of input and output data and can as well be used to customise the membership functions so that the fuzzy system best models the data. Sugeno-ANFIS can model nonlinear functions of arbitrary complexity. It is independence from restrictive assumptions, such as linearity, normality, homoscedasticity and provides promising and acceptable alternatives to traditional stochastic hydrological modelling. In this study, the Sugeno system was optimised using ANFIS for trust evaluation.

2.5 CUSTOMER RELATIONSHIP MANAGEMENT (CRM)

2.5.1 Background to CRM

CRM is an art of building individual relationships with high-value customers to enjoy their continued patronage and archiving a win-win outcome for both the sellers and customers (Soltani and Navimipour 2016). CRM technique allows businesses to organise, automate and synchronise every area of customer interaction (Jafari and Soltani 2016; Arroyo et al. 2017; Kruempelmann and Jacob 2018). This increases customers' loyalties and creates more profit for sellers regardless of any economic conditions. It also allows the customers to receive quality products and services. CRM technique in business-to-business (B2B) e-commerce (EC) involves sellers who manage customers with different perspectives but

working towards the same goal (Gunasekaran et al. 2002). The primary goal of CRM technique is to help businesses perfect the art of customer satisfaction, customer management and resource allocation, which is key to success in any business (Soltani and Navimipour 2016).

Customers believed that they need to trust the business first before they can be committed and loyal to the business (Kingshott et al. 2018; Beitelspacher et al. 2018). Therefore, retaining a customer is the most challenging part of CRM because customers have different motivational factors for choosing a seller (Nguyen and Mutum 2012; Law et al. 2003; Frow and Payne 2009; Hussain et al. 2018). According to Churchill et al. (2016), proper management of customer interactions is a major challenge for modern businesses, especially with the high competition being experienced (Morrison and Crane 2007). Poor CRM outcome can lead to customer loss, business misdirection and eventually complete liquidation of the business (Kim et al., 2018). Besides, lack of commitment from the people within the company when implementing the CRM system can lead to customer relationship breakdown (Moliner et al. 2018).

Several data mining techniques have been proposed for the implementation of different aspects of the CRM system (Krishna and Ravi 2016; Soltani and Navimipour 2016). These can be classified into pure and hybrid data mining techniques such as neural network and chi-square (Krishna and Ravi 2016; Ngai et al. 2009). Others, which have been used to solve CRM tasks which include classification (customer segmentation, churn prediction), clustering (market basket analysis, direct/service marketing), association rule mining (fraud detection), forecasting (default prediction), regression (credit scoring/customer

profiling), sequence discovery (customer lifetime value), and visualization (sentiment analysis) (Payne and Frow 2006; Liao et al. 2012; Ngai et al. 2011). Among all the data mining techniques, classification and association models are the two most widely used for data mining in CRM (Cheng and Chen 2009). However, most of the data mining techniques require optimisation at various stages such as feature selection or determination of the optimal user-defined parameter in order to produce an accurate result (Hong et al. 2018); thereby, reducing the computational speed, increasing computational time, and computational complexity.

This study presents an improved CRM model using Genetic-based Data Mining (GDM) approach to address some of the challenges of CRM. Genetic data mining is a combination of Genetic Algorithm (GA) and data mining. This study uses a combination of data mining and evolutionary computation to optimise the rules generated from the C5.0 algorithm with a genetic algorithm to increase the CRM classification time and accuracy. The C5.0 algorithm was applied to detect and extract hidden customer attributes from large databases, while the GA was applied to utilise processes observed in customer behaviour extracted by the C5.0 algorithm to produce solutions that survive the evolutionary constraints. The GA randomly combines essential function and assign evolutionary goals on the generated algorithms, then recombining the best fitness to form new solutions.

2.5.2 Review of Related Models to CRM

Previous researches have examined CRM in e-commerce environments using different models. One of the models was the Partial focus feature reduction (PFFR). PFFR is a method where the external parameter dictates the number of binary features to be retained from the feature selection process. PFFR technique was proposed to resolved CRM

classification problems with high data imbalance and poor data quality by exploiting the dimensionality reduction phenomenon (Tu and Yang, 2013). PFFR allows characterising a specially tailored modality grouping method to improve data quality and feature relevancy after preprocessing significantly.

Support vector machine, a supervised learning model that analyse data used for classification has also been used for CRM (Yu et al., 2011; Gordini and Veglio, 2017). A hybridised support vector machine (SVM) with Naïve Bayes Tree (NBTree) was used to predict churn in bank credit card customers for CRM purpose was presented. This was achieved in three phases. First, SVM-Recursive feature elimination (SVM-RFE) was applied to reduce the feature set. Second, the support vectors were extracted, and the SVM model was obtained using the reduced features. Finally, rules are generated using NBTree (Farquad et al., 2014).

Concept learning technique (CLT), was employed to solve the communication problem between customers and customer support representatives using direct graphs and classification methods (Galitsky and Rosa 2011; Guan et al., 2015). CLT provides means of training a machine learner to classify objects by being shown a set of example objects along with their class labels. The partial matching of scenarios graph was compared with graphs of positive and negative examples respectively. Joint sparse model (JSM) based on concept learning was used to minimise the number of false negatives and take advantage of a more accurate way of matching sequences of interactive actions (Galitsky and Kuznetsov, 2008).

Self-organizing maps (SOM) and k-means methods were applied in Recency Frequency and Monetary (RFM) model in order to segment customers and develop a CRM system (Wei et al. 2013; Cheng and Chen 2009). The SOM algorithm is based on unsupervised, competitive learning and can recognise and characterise unencountered inputs. However, only particular customer data are included and may thus provide limited marketing implications to managers. Hassan et al. (2015) explored different factors for establishing effective CRM to satisfy and retain the customers. In order to identify independent variables associated with the customers' data that affect any of the dependent variables, regression analysis was used. It was shown that CRM has a significant effect on the customer satisfaction and both variables were positively related.

Autoregressive integrated moving average (ARIMA) was also used for CRM. ARIMA is a forecasting model combined auto-regression analysis and moving average method which is applied to a well behaved time series data. It was argued that customer segmentation based on customer lifetime value and estimating the value of each segment would be useful for deciding on the CRM program using the characteristics of each segment (Javadi and Azmoon 2011). However, since the ARIMA method was only appropriate for a stationary time series, it is assumed that the values of the estimated parameters are constant throughout the series (Yuan et al., 2016; Wang and Hu, 2015). Khajvand and Tarokh (2011) proposed a framework for estimating future customer value based on adapted weighted RFM analysis. K-means algorithm was chosen for customer segmentation using Dunn index. Min-max normalisation method was used to normalise the data while the analytic hierarchy process (AHP) was used to calculate each customer segment value based on adapted weighted RFM model.

A genetic algorithm is an optimisation technique which tries to find out such values of input that can yield the best output results (Mahdavi et al. 2011; Pendharkar 2009). A self-adaptive genetic algorithm was proposed to solve the problem of electronic customer-oriented catalogues in electronic CRM, which can adjust parameters of a genetic algorithm according to the observed performances. It was observed that the self-adaptive genetic algorithm outperforms the Greedy algorithm. However, it was noted that it would be more realistic if the threshold value can be generalised by replacing the crisp threshold by a probabilistic threshold value (Oreski and Oreski, 2014; Hiassat et al., 2017).

Data mining techniques have been widely applied to achieve effective CRM to enable industrial managers to take marketing decisions (Wei et al. 2013). Liao et al. (2012) proposed a data mining approach for exploring online group buying behaviour to help sellers find new ways to sell their products and open up new business models. Apriori algorithm and clustering analysis of the data technique has also been used for CRM. Apriori algorithm is an essential algorithm for frequent mining itemsets for Boolean association rules. Apriori algorithm and clustering analysis were used as an association rules approach and mining customer knowledge among online group buying customers, respectively (Wu, and Sakai, 2015; Liao et al., 2010).

2.5.3 Background to CRM Classification

Customers classification can be described as a way of determining the goodness of customers, based on some selected criteria and the threshold level (Geib et al. 2005; Liao et al. 2012; Chen and Tsai 2016). Customer classification in B2B EC goes beyond the use of the conventional classification method due to customer behaviour about B2B EC (Liu

and Fan 2014) and the number of people involved in the decision making. Based on the selected criteria customers similarities within each of the classes can be used in two ways. First, for segmentation purposes, in order to identify the characteristics of specific criteria that can be used to detect new customers and predict which class they will fall into (Ahn et al. 2011). Secondly for upgrading purposes, to determine whether there are customers that have the potential to be upgraded to higher levels.

In customer classification, every criterion is assigned with different weight. In order to classify the B2B customers with the numbers of criteria and a large number of people involved in the decision making, a novel model for B2B customer classification that will classify customer with accuracy is proposed. Although, other decision tree algorithm such as classification and regression tree, Chi-square automatic interaction detector and the ID3 algorithm may not have optimised the result if used to select the main vital attributes (Yang et al. 2017; Al-sharif et al. 2015).

In this work, B2B customers can be categorised into two different parts using their transaction details; these are a repeat customer and shop-and-go customer. The repeat customer represents the most loyal customers that regularly makes use of the company's services and purchases its products. These kind of customers are the lifeline of any business, and they should be respected and carefully treated. Their lost can impact significantly on the financially and reputation of such business. It has been observed that it could take more work and time to replace a loyal customer than continue to serve them well enough to keep them.

Shop-and-go customers are customers that have done some underground research on what to buy or have an idea of what to buy before taken any further approach to make a purchase. This type of customer has no time browsing through the electronic store, and they can easily be lost to another seller that has what they want. However, it has become an issue for the seller to find out what the requirements are and finding a way to fulfil them. Through proper management practice of active customer relationship, this type of customers can become a valuable repeat customer.

2.6 PURCHASE DECISION-MAKING METHODS

2.6.1 Background to Purchase Decision-Making Methods

The decision-making process in business-to-business (B2B) e-commerce is complicated and frequently characterised by conflict. For instance, the buying process often entails satisfying buyers' demands, which must be met by organisations purchasing the products (Grewal et al., 2015). In most situations, the buying decision is rarely independent of the influence of other stakeholders, who may be either internal or external to the organisation (Canavari et al., 2010; Campanella et al., 2011; Grewal et al., 2015).

In recent times, enormous research efforts have been devoted to addressing various challenges associated with the B2B decision making process and several models have been proposed. The dominant models used for tackling this challenge include the Generalised Vickrey Auction, the analytic hierarchy process (Chen et al., 2008), the fuzzy analytic network process and the Fuzzy-Technique for Order Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (Yu et al., 2011). The Feedback-Based Diagnosis System, ELimination Et Choix Traduisant la REalité (ELECTRE) and Preference Ranking Organisation Methods for

Enrichment Evaluations (Simic' et al., 2016) have also been employed for multi-criteria decision-making to capture the variability and divergence of buyers' judgements.

However, most of these models are primarily based on quantitative evaluations, which affect the economic performance of the organisations. Furthermore, inconsistency was reported in Monte Carlo simulations (Siraj et al., 2015). In most cases, multi-criteria decision-making processes were employed because multiple buyers and customers were involved (Lilien, 2016; Simic' et al., 2016). Thus, there is a need for an effective decision-making scheme that can efficiently handle decision filtering and guarantee consistency.

2.6.2 Related Models to PDM Process

Previous research examined the buying decision-making process in several B2B e-commerce environments using different models. The idea of synthesising buyers' preferences was first introduced in buying decision-making using AHP (Chen et al., 2008). In this framework, individual preferences were synthesised into a group consensus and buyers communicated with each other using a buyer collective process (BCP). A variation of this is a hybrid approach using the analytic hierarchy process and Technique for Order Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (AHP-TOPSIS) to select the best alternatives (Mukherjee, 2014). However, the problem of uncertainty in obtaining the weights for each criterion was introduced - either by objective or subjective methods.

The Feedback-Based Diagnosis System (FBDS) was proposed as a multi-criteria decision-making process (Afef Denguir-Rekik et al., 2009). The variability and divergence of buyers' evaluations were analysed along with their respective criterion to obtain synthetic appraisals, using the weighted arithmetic mean. The system guaranteed that no information

was lost in the collective evaluation process by the consumers' community. To serve as the primary component of the decision model in an organisation, the fusion of different decision-making units was also introduced. In this regard, individual preferences from different perspectives were merged, using the Logic Scoring of Preference (LSP) method to circulate throughout the organisation.

Another frequently used model is the Generalised Vickrey Auction (GVA) which was used to satisfy optimal auction's properties during decision-making when there was no shill bidding (Takahashi and Matsuo, 2012). A coalition structure-based decision method was further proposed for buyers wishing to purchase multiple items. Two steps were considered for determining the right decision, using winners on the buyers' side to build coalitions and winners on the sellers' side using the results from the buyers' side. Notably, GVA has a substantial computational cost, though each developer can procure the components quickly.

In order to deal with uncertainty and vagueness from subjective perception, the fuzzy analytic hierarchy process (F-AHP) and fuzzy Delphi method (FDM) (Büyüközkan, 2004) have also been proposed and employed. These methods ensure certainty within a group decision process and yield more convincing results. However, low consistency was experienced, which affects the choice of the indexes that conform to the universal consensus of the buyers. In order to address this loophole, a decision-making process based on trust and reputation was proposed recently by Chang et al. (2014). In the Chang et al. (2014) model, variable weights and a satisfaction principle were incorporated to solve the

problem of high-risk transactions. Also, the model used k-means clustering to eliminate low rating scores. Unfortunately, the model was only theoretically based.

More recently, other promising algorithms have been proposed. These include the hybrid genetic algorithm (Kuo and Chen, 2004; Simić et al., 2016), ELimination Et Choix Traduisant la REalité (ELECTRE) and the Preference Ranking Organisation Methods for Enrichment Evaluations (PROMETHEE) Models I (Gajić, 2015; Simić et al., 2016), which were proposed for ranking alternatives in the purchasing process. However, in decision-making, the suitability of ELECTRE has been criticised because decision-makers need to know the advantages of one alternative over another to make a good decision (Botti and Peypoch, 2013; Wan et al., 2017). Also, ELECTRE evaluates a criterion even if it has a weight equal to zero, which could be misleading since it does not consider the value of the weights (Peng et al., 2015). On the other hand, PROMETHEE does not provide a structured method for assigning weights, unlike AHP, which decomposes a decision problem into its constituent parts and builds hierarchies based on the criteria (Macharis et al., 2004; Sen et al., 2015). Motivated by the works above in the development of multichannel decision environments, we propose a novel buying decision-making Analytic-MLP model based on AHP and MLP-NN to address the challenge of the occurrence of ranking irregularities encountered, as well as the inconsistency in buyers' opinions associated with AHP.

2.6.3 Background to Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP)

The AHP method involves four stages. First, the problem is modelled as a hierarchy containing the decision goal, the alternatives for reaching it, and the factors for evaluating

the alternatives. In the second stage, priorities are established among the elements of the hierarchy by making a series of judgements based on pairwise comparisons of the elements. The third stage deals with the synthesis of the judgements to obtain a set of overall priorities for the hierarchy while the consistency of the judgements is examined. Lastly, the overall priorities are analysed and the data scaled (Saaty, 2008).

AHP is known for its capacity in ranking, choice making, prioritisation, resource allocation, benchmarking, quality management, conflict resolution, and decision-making. AHP has the advantage of permitting a hierarchical structure of the criteria, which provides users with a better focus on specific criteria and sub-criteria when allocating the weights. It can evaluate quantitative as well as qualitative criteria and alternatives on the same preference scale of nine levels. AHP can foresee support for group level decision-making through consensus by calculating the geometric mean of the individual pairwise comparisons (Macharis et al., 2004).

Table 1: Summary of Related Work

Researchers	Analysis Method	Strength	Weakness
Ngai and Wat, (2005)	Fuzzy Risk Analyzer	The most serious risk item is addressed first.	The prototype only considers the classified risk items in the framework
Lee and Li, (2006)	Fuzzy Delphi Fuzzy Multiple Criteria Decision Making Kano analysis	Improve trading efficiency and lower the cost of collecting information.	A comparative analysis is required
Miao <i>et al.</i> , (2007)	Fuzzy cognitive agents	Application into various e-commerce/business/service applications.	Difficult to represent causal relationships between factors.
Chan <i>et al.</i> , (2008)	Fuzzy inference system	Bargaining agent creates greater customer satisfaction and customer loyalty to the shopping mall.	Customer's preferences not taken into account in the bargaining process.
Wang and Lin, (2009)	Multi-criteria decision-making: Consistent fuzzy preference relation	faster and more efficient than the conventional analytic hierarchy methodologies	Only (n-1) judgments are considered
Liu and Chen, (2009)	Fuzzy AHP	It identify priorities	Still exploratory stage.
Ajayi <i>et al.</i> , (2010)	Fuzzy logic-based information retrieval model	Reduction in response time	A comparative analysis between Mamdani and Sugeno type fuzzy inference systems is needed

Mohanty and Passi, (2010)	Fuzzy Programming	Linear	Degree of customer focus on the final recommended products are derived	Complexity due to large data
Yu <i>et al.</i> , (2011)	AHP and TOPSIS	fuzzy	Significant impacts to the success and efficiency of e-alliance	Subjective or vague data must be considered during the process
Zandi and Tavana, (2011)	Four-phase QFD model	fuzzy	Systematic decision making.	Decision maker's cognitive capabilities is considered.
Chiu <i>et al.</i> , (2012)	Cluster-based rules	fuzzy	Mining of multiple-level association knowledge.	virtual-time databases are used
Büyüközkan and Çifçi, (2012)	Combined of AHP and TOPSIS	fuzzy	Capturing human uncertainty	Quality performance problem
Castro-Schez <i>et al.</i> , (2013)	Hierarchical Decision Support System based on the Fuzzy Repertory Table (HDSS-FRT) method		Models customer behavior when search in database	Little attention is paid to system usability
Lucas <i>et al.</i> , (2013)	Fuzzy Cost-Benefit Analysis		It brings more significance and value to data.	Lack future adaptation and extensions
Zhang <i>et al.</i> , (2013)	Dynamic time decay (DTD)		Improve the authenticity of feedback ratings.	The average trust score has a defined upper limit and will not grow in an unrestricted manner.
Pan <i>et al.</i> , (2014)	Fuzzy multi-objective model		Less computational complexity	The model is used under simplifying assumptions.
Tadic <i>et al.</i> , (2014)	Fuzzy AHP		Effective in big data	Execution time is slow

Huang <i>et al.</i> , (2015)	Fuzzy multi-attribute selection using axiomatic design and the AHP	Facilitate autonomous and auto-buying	both online	Not applicable to real world
Hyun and Luis <i>et al.</i> , (2015)	Fuzzy logic	Calculate user reputation		Efficiency of the review analysis needs to be improve.
Vahidov and Ji, (2017)	Fuzzy weighted-sum model and cluster analysis	Positive impact on customer's trust level.		The effectiveness of the method needs to be tested through statistical hypotheses
Liu <i>et al.</i> , (2017)	Fuzzy e-commerce customer satisfaction index (ECSI)	A five levels quantity based fuzzy index in used		Integrated additional cultural factors are not considered.
Palvia (2017)	Unified model	The model includes the role of good relations with the consumer in ensuring a successful and sustainable relationship. The key relational concepts developed includes customer satisfaction, value, and loyalty.		The study used student subjects to evaluate. Which implies that the result would have reinforced if sample of general e-commerce customers were used. Effect of industry sector, size of the companies, and business strategies were not considered.
Oliveira <i>et al.</i> (2017)	Path model	The overall findings suggested that consumers with high trust demonstrate a higher intention to purchase online.		Only one e-vendor was allowed to be considered by respondents when answering the questionnaire, whereas, this self-selection of e-vendor could influence the results

Wu et al. (2018)	Linguistic principal component analysis	It reduces both dimensions of large-scale attributes and DMs	The interrelation between attributes and social connections between DMs are not considered in process of dimension reduction
De Caigny et al. (2018)	Logit leaf model	Comprehensibility in customer churn is addressed	Problems with handling linear relations between variables and difficulties with interaction effects between variables.

CHAPTER THREE

METHODOLOGY

3.1 OVERVIEW

This chapter presents the methodology for an intelligent B2B architecture, while focusing on three significant aspects of the architecture namely: trust, CRM, and PDM. For each aspect, novel models were proposed to address the challenges pointed out in section 1.3. The mixed method approach comprises both qualitative and quantitative research at the individual and group levels is chosen to analyse the situation from different perspectives and provide a better insight. Different data sources were used to explain the complex phenomenon of the working areas.

3.2 THE PROPOSED B2B ARCHITECTURE

For effective implementation of this research, Figure 4 presents the intelligent evaluation architecture for B2B e-commerce.

Figure 4: An Intelligent Evaluation Architecture for B2B E-Commerce (1a,2a) Evaluate Vendors trust (1b,2b) Vendors trust confirmed (3a,4a) Check Customer relationship management (3b,4b) CRM confirmed (5) Set product goal (6) Process PDM (7) Final product price negotiation (8) Proceed for product payment (9) Payment received (10) Product sent (11) Product delivered to Customer

In any business organisation (consumer) the number of stakeholders involves in making up such organisation determined how complicated and strictly several activities would carry out. In Figure 4, organisation A is planning to place an order for any particular product, however, it is essential to make a critical decision concerning such product. This is due to different individual with different perspective and background involved in the PDM. Moreover, transacting with a trustworthy business organisation (vendor) is of significant due to high capital involved in the B2B transaction. Therefore, the ability to evaluate vendor(s) trust using an efficient algorithm and for the vendor to satisfy and retain prospective customer through useful CRM algorithm for future benefit is necessary.

3.3 B2B E-COMMERCE TRUST MODEL

The proposed trust model for customers' satisfaction and retention is presented in Figure 5. Four metrics, which includes customer-vendor interaction, failure publication, website update and security are used for analysis and evaluation of customer trust. The dimension of customer trust, vis a vis competence, integrity, and benevolence are directly influenced by the metrics of customer trust for the online vendor. In the case, competence represents the skills and resources that would enable the vendor to perform outstandingly among others (Pulles et al., 2014). On the other hand, integrity is the adherence of a vendor to the set of principles that are acceptable to customers who may trust the vendor (Lassoued and Hobbs, 2015). Integrity is an essential factor for a trustee to be trusted by others because there are many uncertainties and risks in e-businesses. Benevolence is the degree of willingness to exercise generosity (Xu et al., 2016). The extent to which a vendor is perceived to have good intention toward others without a profit motive (Paul, 2002).

For this purpose, four hypotheses are set to analyse the metrics as:

H1. Customer-vendor interaction will positively influence the level of trust in customer retention and satisfaction.

H2. Failure publications will positively influence the level of trust in customer retention and satisfaction.

H3. Website update will positively influence the level of trust in customer retention and satisfaction.

H4. Security will positively influence the level of trust in customer retention and satisfaction.

Figure 5: Proposed B2B Trust Evaluation Model

In other words, satisfying and retaining a customer are connected to the level of the competence, integrity, and benevolence of the vendor (Xie and Peng, 2009). The trust dimension checks for correlation between customer and vendor satisfaction. The overall trust level is used to set a trust decision on either to accept or reject a vendor. In Figure 5, Sugeno-ANFIS is used for prediction to deduce whether a customer will be satisfied with the products and services of a business. Sugeno-ANFIS is a combination of fuzzy inference and Artificial Neural Network. The choice of a fuzzy inference system was its ability to use an expert system to simulate the decision-making process, which provides a numerical value as a response (Venturelli et al., 2017).

Customer judgements towards the vendor are gathered using the trust metrics and are used to calculate the overall trust level prediction using Sugeno-ANFIS. Prediction is necessarily on the stage to ascertain future retention of the customers. Based on respondent's analysis, a minimum threshold for the customer trust level was set at ≥ 0.6 so that any value that is less than 0.6 is a rejection. Thus, the overall prediction can either acceptance or rejection of the vendor.

3.3.1 Customer Trust Metrics

In this study, there are two purposes for evaluating customer trust, which is to satisfy and retain customers. Customers trust is a priority in any business strategy. The four customer trust metrics are discussed as follows:

(i) Customer-vendor interaction

Customer-vendor interaction is a mutual communication of business ideas between the customer and the vendor over products, services and negotiation agreement (Kang et al.,

2015). Creating and allowing customer-vendor interaction platform is essential to discover those areas of concern to the customers and how to provide possible resolution for customer convenience. Interaction would improve customer patronage and loyalty, which could later result in customer retention (Nisar and Whitehead 2016). Interaction is needed frequently to improve the understanding of the business, and it indicates how much the customers appreciate the vendor services. It would further serve as an instinct towards the real power to satisfy a customer.

H1. Customer-vendor interaction will positively influence the level of trust in customer retention and satisfaction.

(ii) Failure publications

As the business has its positive side, it is also sometimes faced with some unforeseen conditions that if not dealt with can lead to backwards and failure of the company. To avoid this, the customer can publish some of the drawbacks of a business and most importantly highlight some possible areas identified for improvement (Hoffman et al., 2016). A prompt and positive response to these failures by the vendor would increase customer trust. Failure publication is an avenue for allowing customers' the vendor. Failure publication would give vendors the opportunity to come up with radical solutions needed to tackle the unprecedented challenges faced by the customers. According to business communications expert, "acknowledging inescapable facts" is a central attribute of transparent organisations (Sven, 2016). It is certain that a cover-up policy will hurt twice once discovered.

H2. Failure publications will positively influence the level of trust in customer retention and satisfaction.

(iii) Website update

The growth of a business is reflected in the routine update of the website information. At some duration, positive changes, additions and upgrades are always naturally expected in any growing business website. Website update is an essential way for a vendor to communicate how genuine and effective an e-commerce business is (Laudon and Traver, 2013; Turban et al., 2016). It would give customers the notion of responsibility and reliability of the vendor. In website updates, identified complexity is expected to be significantly reduced to forestall ambiguity and increase trust. Customer trust can be increased in this case by removing uncertainties and focusing on simplifying relevant information about the products and services the company must offer.

H3. Website update will positively influence the level of trust in customer retention and satisfaction.

(iv) Security

In this day of an e-commerce transaction, the customer is becoming more security conscious and curious because much sensitive information, such as personal details and bank passwords with which urge electronic cash are shared and exchanged in a constraint open environment where fast operations are done (Laudon and Traver, 2013). It is important to note that a well secure authentication mechanism will increase customer trust. This implies that an increase in the customer security level will increase customer trust. Security will ensure the safety of the website and the information it contains. When the security of any e-commerce site increases, the customer engagement will also increase (Turban et al., 2018).

H4. Security will positively influence the level of trust in customer retention and satisfaction.

3.3.2 Data Collection and Model Assumption

The data are collected from the responses of a semi-structured interview and questionnaire by prominent users of e-commerce. The interpreted data become the input to the model. Questionnaires were administered via the internet to collect data from participants. The participants were invited through a social media, that is, Facebook invitation and e-mail, which were linked to the survey website uniform resource locator (URL). The questionnaires are composed of nine sections with forty-six questions covering the trust metric variables. Related questions accompany each variable. The method of scoring was chosen based on the Likert scale of 5 degrees in order of intensity in each group from 1 to 5, like (1) Strongly disagree (2) Disagree (3) Neutral (4) Agree (5) Strongly agree (Adelson and McCoach, 2010). The respondents cut across two African countries, Nigeria and Tanzania. Out of 309 responses, 56 were disqualified due to incomplete responses that are very significant. The 253 valid responses represented an overall response rate of 82%. The responses from male and female respondents were 119 (47%) and 134 (53%), respectively with four responses having missing values. Thus, the number of missing values is 0.0158, which is less than 2%. Hence, the mean value was used as a replacement (Alsaad et al., 2017).

3.3.3 Modelling Customer Trust using Sugeno-ANFIS

In fuzzy inference system (FIS), the trust parameters are estimated according to fuzzy rule, unlike other models where the parameters to fit a model on data in classical statistics are estimated by maximum likelihood estimation (Siddall and Kluge, 1997; Du and Swamy,

2013). For trust evaluation, we use the FIS approach, which has some advantages in comparison with other forms of trust evaluation techniques (Venturelli et al., 2017). FIS used to generate a rating for the assessment of the customer satisfaction and retention. In this study, Sugeno-FIS was employed for customer trust evaluation while ANFIS was used for the optimisation of the results derived from Sugeno-FIS.

3.3.4 Sugeno Fuzzy Inference System (Sugeno-FIS)

A fuzzy system contains the knowledge and experience of an expert, in the design of a system that controls a process whose input and output relations are defined by a set of fuzzy control rules (Jantzen, 2013). Fuzzy logic-reasoning contains two types of information. The first is the labels and membership functions (MF) assigned to the input and output variables while the second is related to rule base that processes the fuzzy values of the inputs to fuzzy values of the outputs. In this study, four main stages are used for building the fuzzy logic block: the fuzzification, knowledge base, inference engine and defuzzification. Figure 6 shows the representation of fuzzy logic block.

Figure 6: Fuzzy Logic Block

The Sugeno FIS mapped all the trust input parameters to the input MF. The input MF are mapped to rules, and the rules are mapped onto a set of output parameters. The output parameters are further mapped to the output MF. The firing strength, that is, the impact of the weight on the rules is computed using

$$w_1 = A_1(x_0).B_1(y_0); w_2 = A_2(x_0).B_2(y_0), \quad (1)$$

with $A_1(x)$ and $B_2(x)$ are the membership functions while w_1 and w_2 are the weight for inputs 1 and 2, respectively. In Eq. (1), the $A_1, A_2, B_1,$ and B_2 represent fuzzy sample set of the trust metrics with x_0 and y_0 , which denote the sample input nodes. In Eq. (2), each output rule is derived as a relationship

$$z_1^* = a_1x_0 + b_1y_0; \quad z_2^* = a_2x_0 + b_2y_0. \quad (2)$$

In Eq. (2), the $a_1, a_2, b_1,$ and b_2 represent the sample premise parameters. The z_1^* and z_2^* are the rule output for any input 1 and 2. The weight w_i acted on each output level z_i to produce optimised output level z_0 . The output MF would result into a single-valued decision represented by

$$z_0 = \frac{w_1z_1^* + w_2z_2^*}{w_1 + w_2} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n w_i z_i^*}{\sum_{i=1}^n w_i}, \quad (3)$$

which is called the crisp control. In Eq. (3), the w_i and z_i^* are the i^{th} rule's firing strength and each rule outputs, respectively. While z_0 is the final trust level output. If there exist n rules in the rule-base, then the crisp control action is computed as the combination of w_i and z_i given in Eq. (3). The w_i denotes the firing level of the i^{th} rule, for $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$, with n representing the number of rules and z_i denotes the output level. The weight w_i

acted on each trust metric to produce optimised output level z_i . Table 2 represents the Sugeno inference rules and consists of premises, fact and consequence. In Table 2, p 's are the premises, the *fact* represents the rules that are applied, and z_0 is the consequence. The z_i represents each output at different levels, and the final output is the consequence (z_0).

Table 2: Sugeno Inference Rules for the Trust Metrics

Premise (P_1): if x is A_1 and y is B_1 then $z_1 = a_1x + b_1y$

Premise (P_2): if x is A_2 and y is B_2 then $z_2 = a_2x + b_2y$

Fact: x is \bar{x}_0 and y is \bar{y}_0

Consequence: z_0

Fuzzification

Fuzzification involves domain transformation where crisp inputs are transformed into fuzzy inputs. In this study, fuzzification was done using a Gaussian membership function (GMF) (Li, 2013; Mondal et al., 2016). The GMF provides smooth curve transition between low, medium and high levels compared to triangular and trapezoidal shapes with a sharp straight-line edge. The GMF is used for firing the maximum number of rules in the rule base in order to get a more accurate representation of the input-output relationship (Hameed, 2011). The fuzzy values are computed as

$$Fuzzy\ value = \frac{w_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n w_i} \quad (4)$$

In Eq. (4), w_i represents the individual weight factor in the linguistic variables, $i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n$ and $\sum w_i$ denote the total number of weight factors of size n . The parameter selection for the MF depends on the predicted trust level. Table 3 gives the range of values used in analysing the trust level.

Table 3: The Range of Fuzzy Values

Linguistic variable	Fuzzy value range
Low	$0.0 \leq x < 0.3$
Medium	$0.3 \leq x < 0.6$
High	$0.6 \leq x \leq 1.0$

Knowledge Base

The knowledge base fuzzy inference system represents the fuzzy rules that form the inference engine. The knowledge of an expert is translated into a fuzzy rules if-then-else statement for decision support in the inference engine. The generated linguistic fuzzy rules are given in Table 4, based on expert knowledge of trust evaluation using the four-trust metrics. A total of nineteen (19) rules was generated in this case.

Inference Engine

At the inference engine, logical rules are applied to the knowledge base to derive new information. The root means square (RMS) was employed for the fuzzy inference method (Jang, 1993). The RMS is given by

$$\sqrt{\sum_{k=1}^i R_i^2} = \sqrt{R_1^2 + R_2^2 + \dots + R_i^2}, \quad (5)$$

where R_i are the rules and $R_1^2 + R_2^2 + \dots + R_i^2$ are the sum of different rules with the same conclusion in the fuzzy rule base of Table 4.

Table 4: Linguistic Fuzzy Rule base for Trust Evaluation

Rule No.	Customer-vendor Interaction	Failure Publications	Website Update	Security	Trust level
1	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low
2	Medium	Low	Low	Low	Low
3	High	Low	Low	Low	Medium
4	Low	Medium	Low	Low	Low
5	Low	High	Low	Low	Medium
6	Medium	Medium	Medium	High	High
7	Medium	Medium	High	Medium	Medium
8	High	High	High	High	High
9	Medium	Medium	High	High	High
10	Medium	High	High	Medium	Medium
11	High	High	Medium	Medium	High
12	High	Medium	High	Medium	High
13	High	Low	High	Low	Low
14	Low	High	Low	High	Medium
15	Medium	Medium	Low	Low	Low
16	Medium	Low	Low	Medium	Medium
17	Low	Low	Medium	Medium	Medium
18	Low	Medium	Low	Medium	Low
19	Medium	Low	Medium	Low	Low

Defuzzification

Defuzzification is the process of producing quantifiable results in crisp logic, given fuzzy sets and corresponding membership degrees (Krishna et al., 2015; Mondal et al., 2016). The defuzzification method employed in this study is the centre of area (CoA) due to its simplicity and accuracy (Chung et al., 2015; Lau et al., 2015). In this case, the fuzzy controller was first used to calculate the area under the scaled MF and area within the range of the output variable. The controller then calculates the geometric centre of this area as

$$CoA = \frac{\int_{x_{min}}^{x_{max}} f(x)xdx}{\int_{x_{min}}^{x_{max}} f(x)dx} . \quad (6)$$

The *CoA* is used to calculate the best compromise between multiple output linguistic values. In Eq. (6), x represents the value of the linguistic variables while x_{max} and x_{min} denote the range of the linguistic variables.

3.3.5 Adaptive Network-Based Fuzzy Inference System (ANFIS)

In this study, ANFIS is an adaptive network that uses supervised learning, which helps in the optimisation of the Sugeno-FIS. ANFIS consists of nodes and bonds between the nodes. Some or all the nodes influence the end nodes; therefore, it is adaptive (Svalina et al., 2013; Cosma and Acampora, 2016). Figure 7 shows the block diagram of the ANFIS structure used for the optimisation of Sugeno-FIS arriving at an accurate decision.

Figure 7: The ANFIS Trust Structure

The proposed ANFIS uses a combination of the learning algorithm, least-squares and back-propagation gradient descent methods to model a training data set. ANFIS was also used to validate the model using a checking data set to test for over-fitting of the training data. Given the values of postulate parameters, the final output z_0 can be expressed as a linear combination of the consequent parameters (Jang, 1993; Habib and Akram, 2015), as shown in Eq. (7)

$$\begin{aligned}
 z_0 &= \frac{w_1}{w_1 + w_2} z_1^* + \frac{w_2}{w_1 + w_2} z_2^* = \bar{w}_1 z_1^* + \bar{w}_2 z_2^* \\
 &= (\bar{w}_1 x) p_1 + (\bar{w}_1 y) q_1 + (\bar{w}_1) r_1 + (\bar{w}_2 x) p_2 + (\bar{w}_2 y) q_2 + (\bar{w}_2) r_2. \quad (7)
 \end{aligned}$$

3.3.6 Fixing Sugeno-FIS with ANFIS

In Sugeno-ANFIS structure, the rule base and the membership functions were determined using the input values from Sugeno-FIS. The structure of the proposed Sugeno-ANFIS is presented in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Sugeno-ANFIS Architecture

Figure 8 has five layers with four inputs and one output. The nodes c, f, u and e are the inputs with two fuzzy sets each labelled as A_1, \dots, D_2 (Nilashi *et al.*, 2011). In this case, c, f, u and e represents the inputs for customer-vendor interaction, failure publication, website update, and security, respectively. The output values are the trust level. Output value at each layer is computed using input variables from the previous layer and parameters at each node. From layer 1 to 4, parameters are identified using the least square method with fixed premise parameters, and the product signals are calculated at each node. Nonetheless, the error is transmitted from the output node to the input node from layer 4 to 5 and parameters are modified by the gradient descent method.

Let $O_{l,i}$ is the output of the i th node of the layer l , where l ranges from 1 to 5 in this case.

Every node i is an adaptive node with a node function

$$O_{1,i} = \mu_{A_i}(c). \quad (8)$$

If a trust metric, say c , be the input value, μ_{A_i} is the degree of the membership function of fuzzy set A_i (Suparta and Alhasa, 2016; Chan *et al.*, 2012; Habib and Akram, 2015). Using a Gaussian function, the membership function can be computed as

$$\mu_A(c) = \frac{1}{1 + \left| \frac{x-c_i}{a_i} \right|^{2b_i}}, \quad (9)$$

where a_i, b_i, c_i are the parameter sets referred to as premise parameters and $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$.

Now, the *prod* in Figure 8 represents the product of the input metrics. Thus, in layer 2, the membership functions are multiplied as

$$O_{2,i} = w_{2,i} = \mu_{A_i}(c) \cdot \mu_{B_i}(p) \cdot \mu_{C_i}(u) \cdot \mu_{D_i}(e). \quad (10)$$

Here, each node represents the firing strength, that is, the weight of the rule as given in Eq. (10) (Mondal *et al.*, 2016; Habib and Akram, 2015). In layer 3, the i^{th} node calculates the ratio of the i^{th} rule's firing strength to the sum of all rule's firing strengths as

$$O_{3,i} = \bar{w}_i = \frac{w_i}{w_1 + w_2 + \dots + w_n}. \quad (11)$$

Eq. (11) is a normalized firing strength. Layer 4 is the defuzzifier layer that performs defuzzification to give the crisp output (Habib and Akram, 2015). The outputs at layer 4 are generated by the fuzzy rules with weight factors obtained from layer 3, given as

$$O_{4,i} = \bar{w}_i z_i^* = \bar{w}_i (p_i c + q_i p + r_i u + s_i e + t_i). \quad (12)$$

The \bar{w}_i is the normalised firing strength from layer 3 while p_i, q_i, r_i, s_i , and t_i are the parameter sets referred to as consequent parameters. Layer 5 is a fixed node labelled sum, which computes the overall output as the summation of all incoming signals from layer 4 (Babuška, 2012; Habib and Akram, 2015). The overall output is computed as

$$overall\ output = O_{5,i} = z_0 = \frac{\sum_i w_i z_i^*}{\sum_i w_i}. \quad (13)$$

Considering the goodness-of-fit of the trust metrics, adjusted R^2 was used to analyse the number of predictors for comparisons (D'Agostino, 2017). The adjusted R^2 is given as

$$R_{adj}^2 = 1 - \frac{MS\ Error}{MS\ Total} = 1 - \left\{ \frac{\sum (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}{\sum (y_i - \bar{y})^2} \right\} \left(\frac{n-1}{n-p-1} \right), \quad (14)$$

where y_i , \hat{y} and \bar{y} are the i^{th} observed, fitted and mean responses, respectively. The n and p represent the number of observations and terms, respectively. In the process, the adjusted R^2 converts any negative values to zero.

3.4 THE ADAPTIVE CRM CLASSIFICATION MODEL

An adaptive CRM classification model proposed for this study is shown in Figure 9, which comprises of five dependent stages. The detail explanation for each stage of the proposed adaptive CRM model is described as follows:

Pre-processing (data partition) stage: This stage described the customer dataset partitions into two separate sets (training and testing). The training set has the highest percentage of the dataset (70%), whereas the testing set has 30% of the remaining dataset. This was done in order to have a high level of accuracy and better performance level.

Decision/rules generation stage: At this stage C5.0 algorithm was used, a decision tree algorithm to extract any hidden salient attributes from the training set and generate rules based on this attributes. Unlike other types of decision tree algorithm as mention earlier, C5.0 algorithm was used due to its accuracy, high recognition rate, low complexity, and high adaptability.

Optimization stage: GA was applied for the optimisation of the generated inference rules by the C5.0 algorithm.

Testing stage: The optimised rules were applied to the testing set in order to observe its performance and accuracy and to check the computational speed of the entire process.

Segmentation stage: At the final stage the optimised rules was able to segment the testing set into two different categories repeat customer and shop-and-go (ready-to-buy) customer.

Figure 9: The Proposed Adaptive Genetic-based Data Mining CRM Classification Model

3.4.1 The modified C5.0 Process

In data mining, C5.0 is a supervised classification algorithm that constructs a classifier in the form of a decision tree using information gain (Jansson 2016). C5.0 uses trained dataset labelled in classes to predict the class of a new data. C5.0 makes use of a single-pass pruning process to mitigate over-fitting which improve on the result. C5.0 can work on both continuous and discrete data by specifying ranges or thresholds value for continuous data thereby transforming continuous data into discrete data (Liu and Fan 2014). It has high computational speed, and output is human readable. C5.0 has been modified in execution efficiency and memory (Delen et al. 2013). C5.0 has a boosting technique which further improves the recognition rate of the attributes. Compared to other decision tree algorithms, C5.0 has higher accuracy, high computational speed, and smaller decision tree model that takes up less computer memory (Jansson 2016). Additionally, the character of the C5.0 algorithm includes low complexity, easy and high adaptability. Due to the advantages of the C5.0 algorithm, several researchers have applied the algorithm to different applications (Liu and Fan 2014).

C5.0 generates a decision tree where each node splits the classes based on the gain of information. The decision tree was built from a set of training dataset using the concept of information entropy. The training data is a set of classified samples having P –dimensional vectors defining the attributes of the sample. The attribute with the highest normalisation information gain is used as the splitting criteria (Babu and Ananthanarayanan 2018). The training dataset is a set $D = \{d_1, d_2, d_3, \dots, d_i\}$ of already classified samples. Each sample

d_i consists of a P –dimensional vector $x_{1,i}, x_{2,i}, \dots, x_{p,i}$, where x_i represent the attribute values of customers as well as the class in which d_i falls as describes in Algorithm 1.

3.4.2 Genetic Algorithm (GA) Process

Genetic algorithms (GA) are adaptive heuristic search algorithm that represents intelligent exploitation of a random search used to solve both constrained and unconstrained (based on a natural selection process that mimics biological evolution) optimisation problems (Yang et al. 2016). GA is useful in solving problems that are not well suited for standard optimisation algorithms such as non-differentiable, stochastic, highly nonlinear, or in a situation where the objective function is discontinuous. The GA iteratively modifies a population of individual solutions by randomly selecting individuals from the current population and using them as parents to produce the offspring for the next generation (Liu et al. 2016).

Three main types of rules are used by GA at each step to create the next generation from the current population, these are: (i) selection rules, which select parents that contribute to the next generation population (Carr 2014), (ii) Crossover rules, which combine two parents to form children for the next generation and finally, (iii) mutation rules apply random changes to parents to form children (Carr 2014). The application of GA in this study imitates the biological processes of reproduction and natural selection to solve for the fittest solutions. The optimisation technique allows us to set the level of randomness and the control level (Castillo et al. 2018; Sivanandam and Deepa, 2007).

The following are the description of the five components of a genetic algorithm, which are as follows:

Population of chromosomes: these are the numerical values that represent a customer solution to the problem that the genetic algorithm is attempting to solve. Each customer solutions are encoded as an array of parameter values. The sample space of customer solutions is translated into chromosomes by converting each parameter value into a bit of string (0's and 1's) and then concatenate the parameters end-to-end. However, there are other encoding techniques such as permutations, real numbers, and other objects, but binary chromosomes have remained a suitable method for discrete solution spaces. The random selection of chromosomes represents the first generation or initial population.

Selection operator: this was used to select some of the chromosomes for reproduction based on a probability distribution in Equation 1. Moreover, the fitter a chromosome is, the more chances are to be selected. The probability distribution $P(C_n)$ of chromosome C_n is given by

$$P(C_n) = \left| \frac{f(C_n)}{\sum_{i=1}^{N_{pop}} f(C_i)} \right| \quad (1)$$

where C_n is the Chromosome n , such that n is any random selection, $f(C_n)$ represents the fitness function of C_n , $f(C_i)$ is the fitness function of C_i , C_i is the Chromosome i for $i = 1$ to N .

Crossover operator: all point subsequence of two of the chosen chromosomes are swapped to create two offsprings.

Mutation operator: randomly flips individual bits in the new chromosomes, which means turning 0 into 1 and vice versa. Although the mutation operator can come before the selection and crossover operator, it is a matter of choice.

Fitness function: is the most pivotal parts of this algorithm. The fitness function tests and quantifies how to fit each potential solution in customers is. The fitness function is the step that determines how the chromosomes will change over time. It also determines the difference between the optimal solution and no solution (Sastry et al. 2014).

3.4.3 Genetic-Based Data Mining for CRM Classification

Genetic data mining is an evolutionary computation based data mining, which combined the power of genetic algorithm with the C5.0 algorithm. Notably, the performance of the GA technique is sometimes superior to that of traditional DM techniques using the no-free-lunch theorem (Krishna and Ravi, 2016; Wolpert and Macready, 1997). Moreover, for useful customer classification, DM (C5.0 algorithm) was combined with an optimisation (GA) technique when solving CRM tasks, as shown in Algorithm 1 and 2. The GA tends to maximise the similarity of rules mined from standard C5.0 data with baseline rule set and minimise the similarity of rules mined from abnormal C5.0 data with baseline rule set.

Algorithm 1: An Adaptive C5.0

Input: *FormTree(T)*

Output: *N*

```
1 Compute Class Frequency on (T)
2 if OneClass or FewCases
3   return a leaf
4 end if
5 Create a decision node N
6 foreach Attribute A
7   ComputeGain (A)
8   N.test = AttributeWithBestGain;
9 end for
10 if N.test is continuous
11   find Threshold
12 end if
13 foreach T` in the splitting of T
14   if T` is Empty
15     Child of N is a leaf
16   end if
17   Child of N = FormTree(T)
18   ComputeErrors of N
19   return N
20 end for
```

Algorithm 2: An Adaptive Genetic-based Data Mining

Input: D : Customer Dataset, Parameters

Output: Optimal classification rules

```
1  $T = \{\}$ ;  
2 if  $D$  is Pure OR other stopping criteria met then  
3   break  
4 end if  
5 for all attribute  $a \in D$  do  
6   Compute information theoretic criteria if  $a$  is split  
7 end for  
8  $a^* =$  Best attribute according to the above computed criteria  
9  $T^* =$  Create decision node for finding  $a^*$  in the root  
10  $D^* =$  Sub-dataset from  $D$  based on  $a^*$   
11 for all  $D^*$  do  
12    $T^* = C5.0(D^*)$   
13   Attach  $T^*$  to the corresponding branch of  $T$   
14 end for  
15  $t \leftarrow 0$ ;  
16 initializes the population  $p(t)$   
17 evaluates the population  $p(t)$   
18 while termination condition is not true do  
19   Select the best individuals to be used by the genetic operators  
20   Create a new solution  $p'(t)$  using crossover and mutation  
21   Evaluates the fitness of the new solutions  $p'(t)$   
22   Apply genetic operators  $p'(t) \cup T$  on next generation population  $p(t + 1)$   
23    $t \leftarrow t + 1$   
24 end while  
25 return Optimal classification rules
```

The objective of the GA is to maximise the payoff of customer solutions in the population against fitness function from the problem domain by optimising the rules generated by the C5.0 algorithm. The GA repeatedly employ surrogates for the recombination and mutation genetic mechanisms on the population of customer solution, where the fitness function applied to a decoded representation of a customer governs the probabilistic contributions a given customer solution can make to the subsequent generation of the customer solution.

3.5 PURCHASE DECISION-MAKING (PDM) PROCESS

A PDM process is considered as cognitive, situational, economical and sometimes socio-cultural criteria. B2B buying include those between manufacturers, primary producers as well as wholesalers and retailers involving a far more extensive range of stakeholders who are involved in purchasing processes (Lilien, 2016). B2B buying is tied to a specific business problem with the buying process and the involvement of decision participants (Grawal et al., 2015). In addressing our buying decision-making problem, we consider a typical library and book publishers' scenario as a case study in this work. However, other B2B scenarios such as pharmaceutical firms and both hospitals and physicians; and agribusiness firms and farmers could adequately fit into our model (Lilien, 2016). For instance, with the growing market demand on food for which new primary producers and marketers are often sought on a regular basis; decisions to purchase from a new supplier and market some of these products would depend on some steps (Menard and Klein, 2004; Canavari et al., 2010).

3.5.1 Library-Publishers Scenario

In this work, a novel decision-making process for B2B buying, which combined the best features of an analytic hierarchy process (AHP), analytic network process and Multilayer

Perceptron (MLP) – Analytic-MLP is presented. Using a library-publishers scenario as a prototype procurement decision-making process, we classified the library book factors as the criteria and the publishers as the alternatives in our model. The AHP assigns a weight to each book criterion using a pairwise comparison matrix with an arrangement based on priority. Consistency in the judgement levels was measured based on congruence and dissonance. The ANP leveraged the challenge of independence for these case. The MLP-NN was used to develop specific nonlinear mapping by adjusting the network weights using a learning algorithm.

We consider a library organisation that intends to upgrade its book collections. The library team have to deliberate on which publishers to consider for any collection of books within specific subject areas. Library decision makers consist of the librarian and the heads of departments, namely, Cataloguing Librarian Section (CLS), E-librarian, Information Book Selection Committee (IBSC), will contact other heads of departments to send lists of disciplines or books and journals needed. The decision makers will then contact the book vendors to collate varieties of books from different publishing houses.

In this case, the book's criteria are price, publisher, delivery, trust, delivery, book title, publication period, discount, and author. Their corresponding publishers categorised the listed books into criteria and alternatives. Figure 10 shows the proposed model for the buying decision-making process, consisting of three main phases: the data collection, AHP and ANP, and MLP-NN. The decision to get supplies from some particular publishers would take some procedures as follows:

Step 1: The library team declares the intention to buy some library books from the publishers.

Step 2: The library team gives their perspectives towards the stated goal

Step 3: The perspectives are analysed using AHP and ANP

Step 4: Both AHP and ANP algorithm will compute the information gathered using a pairwise comparison matrix respectively and allocated weight to several criteria, sub-criteria and alternatives. In the AHP, each element in the hierarchy is considered to be independent of all the others. However, in many real-world cases, there is interdependence among items and alternatives. ANP helps in leveraging the problem of independence in these case.

Step 5: The predicted alternatives by the AHP are assigned as input into the MLP-NN

Step 6: The MLP-NN optimised the results provided as inputs by training it to give a precise ranking.

Figure 10: Proposed PDM Process using Analytic-MLP

3.5.2 Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP)

In AHP, the data are derived by using a set of pairwise comparisons. These comparisons are used to obtain the weights of the decision on the criteria, and the alternatives are measured regarding each decision (Saaty, 1987; Triantaphyllou and Mann, 1995). This procedure is divided into four stages: problem definition, an organisation of the decision hierarchy, construction of a set of pairwise comparison matrix and priorities (Teknomo, 2006). The decision hierarchy is organised from the top level (criteria) to the intermediate level (sub-criteria) through the lowest level (alternative).

If we consider N attributes of book criteria (A), the pairwise comparison of i and j attributes yield a square matrix given by

$$Z_{A \times A} = \begin{bmatrix} r_{11} & \cdots & r_{1A} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ r_{A1} & \cdots & r_{AA} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (25)$$

where N represents the comparison number of variables, $r_{11} \dots r_{1A}$ are the alternatives, $r_{11} \dots r_{AA}$ represents the pair-wise comparisons and Z denotes the alternatives with pairwise comparison. In Eq. (1), $Z = r_{ij}$ and $r_{ij} > 0$. When $r_{ij} = 1$ then, $i = j$. A bi-way random index of 1 to 9 (Saaty, 2008) is used for comparison to ascertain the degree of importance of the book's variables.

At the pairwise comparison matrix, each element at the top level is used to compare the element next to it using a random index (RI) values (Saaty, 2008). The priorities obtained from the comparisons are used to weigh the priorities next to it. The relative normalised weight (w_j) of each attribute is analysed by

$$w_j = \frac{GM_j}{\sum_{j=1}^A GM_j}, \quad (26)$$

with GM_j being the geometric mean and $\sum_{j=1}^A GM_j$ denoting its normalisation (Alam *et al.*, 2012; Cay and Mevlut, 2013). Eq. (26) determines the weights of the criteria. The composite performance scores of the criteria of the weight are computed using

$$C_i = \sum_{j=i}^A w_j (m_{ij})_{normal} . \quad (27)$$

In Eq. (27), the alternatives are attained by multiplying the relative weight (w_j) of each attribute in Eq. (26) with its respective normalised weight value for each alternative and summing up the overall attributes for each alternative in Eq. (27). The $(m_{ij})_{normal}$ represents the normalised value of m_{ij} and C_i is the composite score of the alternative A_i . The procedure accepts the users' perspectives, a combination of library team and publishers as inputs based on the criteria and sub-criteria. To measure the consistency level, we defined congruence (Θ_{ij}) as

$$\Theta_{ij} = \frac{1}{n-2} \sum_{k=1}^n |\log(a_{ij}) - \log a_{ik} a_{kj}| \quad (28)$$

and dissonance (ψ_{ij})

$$\psi_{ij} = \frac{1}{n-2} \sum_{k=1}^n \text{step}(-\log a_{ij} \log a_{ik} a_{kj}), \quad (29)$$

where $i \neq k \neq j$ and the step function is defined by $\text{step}(x) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } x > 0 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$. The set of values ψ_{ij} constructed forms a dissonance matrix that can supplement the congruence matrix in order to spot the most inconsistent judgments. Therefore, Eq. (28) and Eq. (29) are used simultaneously to detect and highlight outlying judgments (Siraj *et al.*, 2015).

The congruence test between pairwise comparison, that is, $r_{ij} = r_{ik} * r_{kj}$, for all i, j, k , is considered. If the decision-making judgments are cardinaly inconsistent, then at least one indirect judgment $a_{ik} * a_{kj} \neq a_{ij}$ is obtained for some i, j , and k where $i \neq k \neq j$ and Θ_{ij} is

a function determining the deviation between a direct and indirect judgment for $i, j, k = 1, 2, \dots, A$. An objective function is formulated and minimized for total deviation between the given judgments a_{ij} and the estimated weights w is analysed with distance function of the total deviation defined by

$$TD(w) = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n \left(a_{ij} - \frac{w_i}{w_j} \right)^2 . \quad (30)$$

In Eq. (30), $\sum w_i = 1$, $w_i > 0$ and $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$. When $a_{ij} > 1$, then the estimated priority vector should preserve the preference direction, which implies that $w_i > w_j$. However, when $w_i < w_j$, it implies that a priority violation has occurred. To forestall this, a minimisation of second-order deviations $TD2$ is calculated using

$$TD2(w) = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n \sum_{k=1}^n \left(a_{ik} a_{kj} - \frac{w_i}{w_j} \right)^2 . \quad (31)$$

Eq. (31) is used to account for the inconsistency when $TD(w)$ produces solutions with a higher number of violations (NV). Thus, we look for the minimum to the transpose of the total deviation with its second order, and the number of violations is given by:

$$\text{minimize}[TD(w), TD2(w), NV(w)]^T . \quad (32)$$

3.5.3 Analytic network process (ANP)

Satty, (2008) first proposed an analytic network process (ANP). ANP deal with interdependent relationships within a multi-criteria decision-making model. The main steps in implementing ANP are as follows (Bhattacharya et al., 2014; Yücenur et al., 2011). Firstly, constructing pairwise matrices of the components with fuzzy judgments and determining the local priorities, consistency index from each matrix using the fuzzy prioritisation method. Secondly, checking the consistency index and aggregate local priorities into group priorities using nonlinear programming approach. Thirdly, filling the

super matrix with the elicited group priorities to form an unweighted super matrix, and obtain weighted super matrix by multiplying the unweighted super matrix by the corresponding cluster priorities, and then adjusting the resulting super matrix to column stochastic. Lastly, limit the weighted super matrix by raising it to sufficiently large power so that it converges into a stable super matrix (all columns being identical) and normalise the scores of alternatives from the limit weighted super matrix into final priorities.

3.5.4 Combination of AHP and Multilayer Perceptron Neural Network (MLP-NN)

An MLP maps a set of input data onto a set of suitable outputs. It consists of input, hidden and output layers. The input neurons, in this case, are based on the results from the AHP and ANP module while the hidden layer performs a linear combination of a sigmoid function of the inputs. Figure 11 shows a combination of AHP/ANP and MLP-NN models with Figure 11a showing the AHP/ANP module, while Figure 11b is a 5-3-2 tier MLP comprising of one hidden layer with three nodes. The hidden layer computes first, a linear combination of the outputs of the neurons of the input layer, plus a bias. The coefficients of the linear combinations and the biases represent the weights.

We used backwards propagation (BP) learning parameters determination proposed by Kecman (2001) with a recommended range of 0 to 8 for both learning rate η , and momentum coefficient β . The transfer function $f(net)$ is given as

$$f(net) = \frac{1}{1+e^{-net}} \quad (f \text{ is in } 0 \sim 1) , \quad (33)$$

with values within 0~1 in Eq. (33) and the log-sigmoid function is used at the hidden and output layers representing the transfer function with e as the error value (Huang and Yoon,

2011). The horizontal and vertical momentums of the weight in the inertia effect of the adjustment are

$$\Delta w_{kj} = \eta(d_k - p_k)f'_k(net_k)p \quad (34)$$

and

$$\Delta w_{ji} = \eta\left[\sum_{k=1}^K(d_k - p_k)f'_k(net_k)w_{kj}\right]f'_j(net_j)p_{yb}, \quad (35)$$

respectively. The weights are used as coefficients adjustment using the least-squared error in Eq. (34) and gradient descent methods in Eq. (35). The p_k signifies the input vector from AHP with normalised neurons, while w_{kj} is the weight value between the nodes, t is the index of iteration, net represents the sum of the product of inputs and the weighting coefficients. x is the input data vector with five features that have been normalised, w is the connection weights between nodes of two layers, p_{yb} is the output value and d_k denotes the desired output.

The final adjustment is the change in weight defined as

$$\Delta w_{ji}(t) = \eta\left[\sum_{k=1}^K(d_k - p_k)f'_k(net_k)w_{kj}\right]f'_j(net_j)p_i + \beta\Delta w_{ji}(t - 1), \quad (36)$$

where η and β in Eq. (36) are the learning rate and momentum coefficient, respectively.

Figure 11: Analytic-MLP process (a) illustrates the AHP/ANP technique using PCM on each criterion, which was later used to derive the alternative products for the target goal. (b) Describes the MLP technique making use of the alternatives generated by AHP/ANP as input

Algorithm 3: The HyperTernary Algorithm

Input: [Dataset(D), Tree(T)] [Normalized training sets(X), Normalized test sets(x), Classes of all training sets(Y)] [CVI, Wu, Fp, Se]

Output: [Optimal customer classification rules] [Optimal customer purchase decision]
[Optimal vendor trust level]

```
1  if  $D, T$  then
2     $T = \{\}$ 
3    if  $D$  is Pure OR other stopping criteria met then
4      break
5    end if
6    for all attribute  $a \in D$  do
7      Compute information theoretic criteria if  $a$  is split
8    end for
9     $a^* =$  Best attribute according to the above computed criteria
10    $T^* =$  Create decision node for finding  $a^*$  in the root
11    $D^* =$  Sub-dataset from  $D$  based on  $a^*$ 
12   for all  $D^*$  do
13      $T^* = C5.0(D^*)$ 
14     Attach  $T^*$  to the corresponding branch of  $T$ 
15   end for
16   Initializes the population  $p(t)$ 
17   Evaluates the population  $p(t)$ 
18   while termination condition is not true do
19     select the best individuals to be used by the genetic operators
20     create a new solution  $p(t)$  using crossover and mutation
21     evaluates the fitness of the new solutions  $p(t)$ 
22     apply genetic operators  $p(t) \cup T$  on next generation population  $p(t + 1)$ 
23      $t = t + 1$ 
24   end while
25   return Optimal customer classification rules
26 else if  $x, X, Y$  then
27    $x =$  Normalized training sets
28    $X =$  Normalized test sets
```

```

29  Y = Classes of all training sets
30  [N, d] = size(X) // N → training sets in d-dimension
31  U = unique(Y) // U → unique training classes
32  M = count(Uc) // M → Number of unique classes
33  W = AHP_ANP(X,Y,Uc,M)
34  [Nt, d] = size(x) // Nt → test sets in d-dimension
    continue
35  for i in 1 to Nt do
36      Dw(t) = dist(x(l),X(t),W) ∀ t ∈ [1,N]
37      [Ds, Is] = sort(Dw) // Ds → sorted distances, Is → sorted indices
38      Ys = Y(Is) // Ys → sorted classes
39      Train MLP using solution Ys
40      Evaluate MLP model and calculate the finally output
41  end for
42  return Optimal customer purchase decision
43 else if CVI or Wu or Fp or Se then // CVI → customer-vendor interaction; Wu → website
    update; Fp → failure publication; Se → security
44  determining a set of fuzzy rules
45  fuzzifying the trust input membership functions to crisp input
46  combining the fuzzified inputs according to the fuzzy rules to establish a rule strength
47  combining the consequences to get an output distribution, and
48  defuzzifying the crisp output distribution
49  Optimize the FIS given actual input classification data
50  Set up training and testing matrices. // The training and testing matrices will be
    composed of inputs and the desired classification corresponding to those inputs
51  Run the ANFIS algorithm on the training data
52  Test the results using the testing data
53  return Optimal vendor trust level
43 end if

```

CHAPTER FOUR

IMPLEMENTATION, RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 INTRODUCTION

This Chapter explains how the proposed HyperTernary model's approach to CRM, PDM, and CSR was carried out. Section 4.2 describes the dataset used for the study, Section 4.3 describes the system specification. Section 4.4 shows the implementation screenshots while Sections 4.5, 4.6, and 4.7 describes the proposed system's results and evaluation. Section 4.8 presents the discussion of the results.

4.2 DATASET

The proposed HyperTernary model was tested on data gotten from B2B e-commerce website and through questionnaires. Questionnaires were administered to B2B e-commerce experts as a primary source of data. The secondary data were gotten from www.jumia.com, www.publishersweekly.com, www.konga.com and kaggle.com.

4.3 SYSTEM SPECIFICATION

The system specification used for the implementation of the system is defined both in terms of hardware and software requirement. The details of these requirements are presented in the next subsections.

4.3.1 Hardware Requirement

The minimum hardware requirements on which the proposed system was implemented, should have the following hardware configuration:

- (i) PC workstation with Intel core i3 processor at 2.40Hz
- (ii) 4GB of RAM

(iii) 5.1 SVGA or VGA with desktop performance for windows

(iv) 88.6MB/s primary disk data transfer and 500GB hard disk capacity

(v) A keyboard and a mouse

4.3.2 Software Requirement

The software requirement for the proposed system are as follows:

(i) Windows 10, Windows 8 or Windows 7

(ii) Python Programming language, Django Framework, MySQL, PriEsT, XGBoost

4.4 IMPLEMENTATION SCREENSHOTS

This section describes the pictures taken during and after the implementation. Figure 12 shows the home or starting page of the system environment. It shows the three modules that make up the HyperTernary model. Figure 13 shows a screenshot of the purchase decision-making. The interface comprises of the pairwise comparison matrix for the product attributes, the vendor score rank and the final purchase decision result. Figure 14 shows a screenshot of the customer satisfaction and retention with a vendor trust evaluation interface based on the four matrices (customer-vendor interaction, failure publication, website update, and security). In addition, Figure 14 shows the interface for each vendor satisfaction level and trust evaluation which represents the level of customer retention. Figure 15 shows the sample dataset used in the implementation of the HyperTernary system.

Figure 12: Home Page for the HyperTernary System

B2B System! Makinde Ayodeji

Welcome, Makinde Ayodeji

Purchase Decision Making Search for... Go!

Pairwise Comparison Matrix (Product Attributes)

Attribute 1	vs	Attribute 2	Score
Price	vs	Discount	4
Publishe	vs	Author	3
Delivery	vs	Discount	1/2
Title	vs	Author	1/6
Trust	vs	Publishe	6
Price	vs	Delivery	1/3
Publicati	vs	Author	1/9
Discount	vs	Publicati	7
Delivery	vs	Publishe	9
Author	vs	Price	5

Vendor 1 | **Vendor 2** | **Vendor 3**

Book B
Total Score: 9.4624
 Vendor 3

Final Purchase Decision Result

After several runs of the purchase decision Book B of Vendor 3 gets the highest Scores in all Author Books.

Would you accept this result?

Figure 13: Purchase Decision-making Interface

Figure 14: Product Management Interface

1	InvoiceNo	StockCode	Description	Quantity	InvoiceDate	UnitPrice	Customer	Country	Dependant
2	536365	85123	WHITE HANGING HEART T-LIGHT HOLDER	6	12/01/2010	78	17850	United Kir	2
3	536365	71053	WHITE METAL LANTERN	6	12/01/2010	95	17850	United Kir	2
4	536365	84406	CREAM CUPID HEARTS COAT HANGER	8	12/01/2010	79	17850	United Kir	2
5	536365	84029	KNITTED UNION FLAG HOT WATER BOTTLE	6	12/01/2010	95	17850	United Kir	2
6	536365	84029	RED WOOLLY HOTTIE WHITE HEART.	6	12/01/2010	95	17850	United Kir	2
7	536365	22752	SET 7 BABUSHKA NESTING BOXES	2	12/01/2010	133	17850	United Kir	2
8	536365	21730	GLASS STAR FROSTED T-LIGHT HOLDER	6	12/01/2010	107	17850	United Kir	2
9	536366	22633	HAND WARMER UNION JACK	6	12/01/2010	44	17850	United Kir	2
10	536366	22632	HAND WARMER RED POLKA DOT	6	12/01/2010	44	17850	United Kir	2
⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮
4666	581585	23145	ZINC T-LIGHT HOLDER STAR LARGE	12	12/09/2011	30	15804	United Kir	1
4667	581585	22466	FAIRY TALE COTTAGE NIGHT LIGHT	12	12/09/2011	45	15804	United Kir	1
4668	581586	22061	LARGE CAKE STAND HANGING STRAWBERRY	8	12/09/2011	82	13113	United Kir	3
4669	581586	23275	SET OF 3 HANGING OWLS OLLIE BEAK	24	12/09/2011	33	13113	United Kir	3
4670	581586	21217	RED RETROSPOT ROUND CAKE TINS	24	12/09/2011	140	13113	United Kir	3
4671	581586	20685	DOORMAT RED RETROSPOT	10	12/09/2011	130	13113	United Kir	3
4672	581587	22631	CIRCUS PARADE LUNCH BOX	12	12/09/2011	45	12680	France	1
4673	581587	22556	PLASTERS IN TIN CIRCUS PARADE	12	12/09/2011	40	12680	France	1
4674	581587	22555	PLASTERS IN TIN STRONGMAN	12	12/09/2011	40	12680	France	1
4675	581587	22728	ALARM CLOCK BAKELIKE PINK	4	12/09/2011	99	12680	France	1
⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮

Figure 15: Database for the HyperTernary model Implementation

4.5 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND EVALUATION FOR CUSTOMER

TRUST LEVEL

In this study, the trust level of customers was analysed using two methods: statistical and Sugeno-ANFIS methods. The statistical method was done using regression analysis and correlation matrix. The regression analysis tests for the overall significance of each trust metric was carried out using the *f-value*, *p-value* and adjusted R^2 . The correlation matrix tests of the reliability of each trust metric were carried out using composite reliability, mean, standard deviation, standard error and correlation.

On the other hand, simulation of the Sugeno-ANFIS was done to derive the trust level using the four metrics by constructing a fuzzification with Gaussian membership function. A knowledge-based FIS was used to form the inference engine. The root means square was used for the inference engine which generates the fuzzy rules based on expert knowledge. The CoA was employed for the defuzzification of the fuzzy rules into a crisp output. The ANFIS made use of a supervised learning backward propagation algorithm for the optimisation of Sugeno-FIS and the final prediction of the trust level.

4.5.1 Trust Metrics Evaluation and Hypotheses

The survey shows that 87.5% of respondents agreed with failures publication, 76.7% of respondents agreed with security, 49.8% of respondents were concerned about customer-vendor interaction and 38.2% of respondents agreed with website update, as shown in Table 5. In general, 96% of the participants argue that the trust metrics will significantly increase the trust level of any B2B e-commerce vendor. The corresponding weights for the trust metrics are also shown in Table 5.

Table 5: Trust Metrics' Weights

Trust Metric	Response rate (%)	Weight (100%)
Customer-Vendor Interaction	49.8	20
Failures publication	87.5	33
Website update	38.2	15
Security	76.7	32

In Table 6, a *t*-test was employed to estimate the significance levels for the stated hypotheses of the research model. From Table 6, the hypotheses for customer-vendor interaction, failure publication, website update and of security yielded $\alpha=0.274$, $\alpha =0.251$, $\alpha=0.185$ and $\alpha=0.357$ with $p<0.05$, respectively. This denotes that all the hypotheses are supported for explaining trust and yielded the acceptance rate.

Table 6: Hypotheses Results

Hypotheses	Trust Metrics	Findings	Positive Significant
H1	Customer-vendor interaction	($\alpha=0.274;p<0.05$)	Yes
H2	Failure publication	($\alpha=0.251;p<0.05$)	Yes
H3	Website update	($\alpha=0.185;p<0.05$)	Yes
H4	Security	($\alpha=0.357;p<0.05$)	Yes

4.5.2 Regression Analysis and Reliability of Measurements

The regression results are shown in Table 7. The *f-values* and adjusted R^2 are computed for the overall significance of each trust metric. All the metrics yielded significant *p-values* ($p < .01$) level. In other words, the tested trust metrics have a highly significant impact on the proposed model. This implies that changes in the trust metric's value correspond to changes in the customers' retention and satisfaction.

Table 7: Summary of regression analysis

Regression Statistics	Customer-vendor interaction	Failure publication	Website update	Security
<i>f</i> -value	6.38	6.75	5.69	7.86
<i>p</i> -value	.00*	.00*	.00*	.00*
Adjusted R^2	0.71	0.73	0.69	0.77

* $P < .01$

Table 8 shows the correlation metrics with composite reliability. The composite reliability scores are higher than the threshold of 0.6. The result in Table 8 implies that reliability scores are highly satisfactory. The correlations among the various trust metrics recorded in Table 8 shows that there is adequate discriminant validity among the various trust metrics. The diagonal element is higher than the correlation between the latent trust metrics. This implies that the trust metrics have higher variance compared to some other latent trust metrics that were not used in this study.

Table 8: Correlation of the Trust Metrics

Metrics	Composite Reliability	Mean	S.D.	S.E.	Correlation			
					<i>C</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>u</i>	<i>e</i>
<i>C</i>	0.9776	7.1111	0.7817	0.2605	1			
<i>F</i>	0.9942	8.5556	0.5270	0.1757	-0.16855	1		
<i>u</i>	0.8958	6.6667	0.7071	0.2357	0.075378	0.223607	1	
<i>e</i>	0.8875	8.3333	0.7071	0.2357	0.829156	-0.22361	0.25	1

Figure 16 shows the effectiveness of customer-vendor interaction and website update against switching costs. It was found that customer-vendor interaction highly reduces switching costs rate that may be incurred by competitors. Therefore, increase the probability of customer retention. Moreover, a timely update of the vendor website has a positive significant on reducing potential customer switching.

Figure 16: Effect of customer-vendor interaction and website update on switching costs

4.5.3 Sugeno-ANFIS Analysis

The proposed Sugeno-ANFIS model was implemented using MATLAB. Figure 17 and 18 shows a rule viewer of the Sugeno inference, which presents the rule-map of the fuzzy inference system. Each rule is delineated by a row of plots, and each column is a variable. Figure 17, the first four columns show the membership functions, referenced by the premises, while the fifth column shows the membership function, referenced by the consequence. The extra plot at the bottom of the fifth column represents the aggregate weighted decision for the given inference system. The red vertical lines at the four premises show the point for the defuzzified output. Each premise shows its variable with the current value. When the defuzzified output of the premises is on average in Figure 17, the aggregate weighted decision of the trust is 0.523. When the premises values were adjusted in Figure 18, the trust level increased to 0.99. This shows that a slight increase in the level of the trust metrics will experience a more considerable increase in trust of the customer.

Figure 19 shows that the trust level is positively related to the level of customer-vendor interaction, failure publication, website update and security. In Figures 19(a), 19(b) and 19(c), the highest gradient for trust increases when a customer-vendor interaction, failure publication and website update is against security. Failure publication and security increases from medium to high. On the other hand, Figure 19(c) and 19(d) shows that website update does not really increase the trust level. However, when failure publication and website update is high, the trust level will increase as shown in Figure 19(e). Thus, implying that the website should be constantly updated with failure publication to boost customer's trust level.

Figure 17: Sugeno-ANFIS rule Viewer for Premises and Consequence

Figure 18: Sugeno-ANFIS rule Viewer for Adjusted Premises

Figure 19: Sugeno-ANFIS 3D surface viewer (a) failures publication against security, (b) Customer-Vendor Interaction (CVI) against security, (c) failures publication against CVI, and (d) site update against CVI (e) Website update against Failure publication (f) Website update against Security

The performance of the proposed trust evaluation model using Sugeno-ANFIS was compared to that of Dynamic time decay, Path model, and Unified model as shown in Table 9. The data collected from respondents were used to evaluate each model. The result shows that our proposed model has a higher impact on customer trust in an e-commerce environment with 98.7% of accuracy. Thus, the Sugeno-ANFIS techniques showed significant enhancement in the customer trust level. However, the computational time for the proposed Sugeno-ANFIS was a bit higher than the compared one because of the Gaussian method that was used for the membership function.

Table 9: Comparison of Trust Evaluation Model based on Accuracy

Model	Accuracy (%)	Computational time (ms)
Dynamic time decay (DTD) (Zhang <i>et al.</i> , 2013)	90.2	8.09
Path model (Oliveira <i>et al.</i> , 2017)	94.6	8.13
Unified model (Palvia, 2009)	88	7.98
Proposed Sugeno-ANFIS	98.7	8.21

Figures 20(a) and 20(b) show the effects of changes in the precision and threshold level on the value of trust respectively for the unified model, DTD, path model and Sugeno-ANFIS model. An increase in the model precision and threshold increases the trust level. Figure 20(b) shows a cumulative curve of the Sugeno-ANFIS with a trust level of 60% at a threshold level of 6 which is equivalent to the proposed 0.6 when compared to other tested models which are below 50% trust level. The results obtained using Sugeno-ANFIS were better than those obtained by the unified model, DTD, and path model on average regarding trust level.

Figure 20: Trust level Comparison, effect of change in (a) Precision on Trust Level, (b) Threshold on Trust Level

4.6 EVALUATION OF CRM

The B2B CRM process, using genetic data mining as described in Section 3, was implemented in R software package, using a construction company scenario as a B2B prototype. Data from December 1, 2010 to December 9, 2011 were collected from Kaggle (www.kaggle.com), comprises of 2685 transactions from 243 customers in different counties. This data set has six feature attributes with five predictors and one target, each customer is either classified as a repeat or shop-and-go customer. The attributes information is as shown in Table 10. 70% of the dataset were selected as training data and the rest as testing data.

Table 10: B2B Customer Attributes Information

Attribute	Type	Value	Description
Invoice Number	Numeric	None	How many invoices did the customer owns?
Price	Decimal	None	How much did the customer spent on products?
Customer ID	Numeric	None	How many time has the customer made transaction?
Quantity	Numeric	None	How many products are purchase at one instance?
Stock Code	Numeric	None	What type of product is being purchase by the customer?
Transaction date	Date	None	How many time has the customer come back?
Class	Categorical	<i>Repeat</i> <i>Shop-and-Go</i>	The class which the customer belong to

The rules were generated after running the C5.0 algorithm as shown in Table 11. The most important attribute that influences the classification result are invoice, unit transaction date, price, and quantity. The random forest in R statistical package (Boruta) is used to predict the most important attribute. If the total number of invoice made by a customer is ≥ 10 and the transaction date is ≥ 5 and quantity per each transaction date is > 3 , the customer will belong to the *repeat* customer class with 83.21% accuracy. If the invoice-number is < 3 and the transaction date is ≤ 1 and the quantity is < 10 , the customer will belong to *shop-and-go* customer class with 72.1% accuracy. The less important attribute is the stock code, customer ID, and unit price. If the unit price is < 50.6 and the quantity is < 3 , then the customer will belong to *shop-and-go* class with 88.4% accuracy. From the description, the most important factors are the transaction date and invoice number, and the less important is the stock code.

Table 11: Rules Generated

ID	Rule	C5.0 Prediction Accuracy
1	If invoice ≥ 10 AND transaction date ≥ 5 AND quantity > 3 THEN class = <i>repeat</i>	83.21%
2	If invoice < 3 AND transaction date ≤ 1 AND quantity < 10 THEN class = <i>shop-and-go</i>	72.1%
3	If unit price < 50.6 AND quantity < 3 THEN class = <i>shop-and-go</i>	88.4%

4.6.1 Genetic-Based Data Mining Algorithm Analysis

In this subsection, the proposed algorithm is analysed. First, by comparing the C5.0 algorithm result with other classification algorithms. Then the genetic algorithm is applied to optimise the generated rules, which is then used for the test set. The result from the genetic data mining is then compared with the previously stated classification algorithm.

To verify the prediction accuracy of the C5.0 algorithm, 299 cases were considered for testing. The C5.0 was able to correctly predicted 258 cases as repeat customers, in which 54 customers were involved, and correctly predicted 18 cases as shop-and-go customers, in which ten customers were involved. However, 2 and 11 cases were wrongly predicted as shop-and-go and repeat respectively. This cases involved nine customers, and the test was done after ten trials on the training set in order to increase the level of accuracy. Unlike k-means and SVM that had 84.6% and 86.21% accuracy respectively, C5.0 algorithm has 78.1% accuracy. Though it can be seen quite well that the accuracy of SVM and k-means are higher than that of C5.0 algorithm, however, rules generated by SVM and k-means are hard to interpret compared to that of C5.0 shown in Table 11. Table 12 shows the evaluation on the training dataset after ten trials, which comprises of 700 cases. The attribute usage in percentage before and after the trials is shown in Table 13. It was found that two *repeat* customers were miss-classified as *shop-and-go* after the optimisation algorithm has acted on the training data.

Figures 21 and 22, depict the superimpose histogram density curves which show the deviation of the quality and price data distribution against customers invoice for the normal

distribution. It was found that most repeat customers tend to occur between product quantity of 5 to 23 and price of 48.5 to 105.

Figure 21: Superimposed Density Curve over a Histogram for Quantity Attribute

Figure 22: Superimposed Density Curve over a Histogram for Price Attribute

Table 12: Evaluation on Training Dataset after 10 trials

Trial	Decision tree (Errors)
0	14 (2.0%)
1	43 (6.1%)
2	80 (11.4%)
3	107 (15.3%)
4	46 (6.6%)
5	20 (2.9%)
6	49 (7.0%)
7	42 (6.0%)
8	61 (8.7%)
9	14 (2.0%)
boost	2 (0.3%)

Table 13: Attribute usage on the Training Dataset

	Before		After	
	<i>Repeat</i>	<i>Shop-and-Go</i>	<i>Repeat</i>	<i>Shop-and-Go</i>
<i>Repeat</i>	654	2	656	2
<i>Shop-and-Go</i>	12	32	10	32

Using the experimental parameter value shown in Table 14, a genetic algorithm was able to effectively optimise the generated rules as well as the level of accuracy. Therefore, putting the accuracy of the four algorithms together as shown in Table 15, proved that the proposed genetic data mining is superior to C5.0, SVM and k-means. The proposed algorithm has low computational time and highly adaptable. The weighting coefficient was adapted from (Liu and Fan 2014). Also in Table 15, it was clearly shown how valid and reliable the proposed GDM model is in term of computational time. There is no doubt that the GDM model supersedes other CRM techniques compared within this study.

Table 14: Genetic Algorithm Parameter Value

Parameter	Value
Mutation probability	0.01
Crossover probability	1
Maximum number of iteration	600
Weighting coefficient	$a = 0.1, b = 0.1, c = 0.2, \text{ and } d = 0.6$

Table 15: Comparison of Accuracy

	Training set (%)	Test set (%)	Computation time (ms)
C5.0	80.52	78.1	6.52
K-means	89.33	90.6	6.95
SVM	90	93.21	7.11
GDM	96.7	98.3	6.47

Figure 23 shows the plot predicted probability against all predicted models. The rug points towards the left at the bottom of the graph are the instances correctly assigned a low probability of the target class. More also, the instances to the right at the top of the graph are correctly assigned high probability. In addition, the diagonal line represents the optimal behaviour of the models. Thus the closer the model's curves gets to the diagonal, the more accurate its prediction probability.

Figure 23: Calibration plot for the GDM Prediction

Figure 24 shows the convex ROC curves for each tested models. The curve plots a false positive rate (1-specificity) against a true positive rate (sensitivity). The closer the curve follows the left-hand border and then the top border of the ROC space, the more accurate the model.

Figure 24: ROC curve for the GDM Prediction

4.7 EVALUATION OF PDM

The buying decision-making process, using Analytic-MLP as described in Section 3, was implemented in PriEsT and MATLAB, using a library-book publishers' scenario as a B2B prototype. Data from 2014 to 2016 were collected from www.publishersweekly.com for 60 publishers. The experiment was set up with 60 publishing companies for possible buying decisions. The library teams were required to recommend publishers for book orders for the library. From the pool of 60 publishers, 29 publishers emerged from a random selection of individual judgments of books by the library's decision-makers. These publishers were used in this study. Table 16 shows the recommended publishers.

Table 16: Recommended Publishers

Publishers	Textbook Buy	Recommended Textbook	(R) R (%)
Reed Elsevier	50	23	8.81
Wolters Kluwer	23	20	7.66
ThomsonReuters	86	37	14.18
Pearson	72	39	14.94
Wiley	58	26	9.96
Holtzbrinck	21	13	4.98
McGraw-Hill Education	16	9	3.45
Oxford University	23	11	4.21
Shogakukan	2	5	1.92
Informa	3	7	2.68
Phoenix Publishing and Media Company	1	3	1.15
Springer Science and Business Media	20	13	4.98
Houghton Mifflin Harcourt	5	8	3.07
Shinchosha	2	2	0.77
Groupe Albin Michel	2	1	0.38
Cambridge University Press	11	8	3.07
Scholastic (corp.)	-	1	0.38
De Agostini Editore	1	1	0.38
Shogakukan	1	1	0.38
China Publishing Group Corporate	3	2	0.77
Hachette Livre	11	7	2.68
De Agostini Editore	3	2	0.77
Mondadori	1	1	0.38
Messengerie/GeMS	8	4	1.53
Media Participations	3	2	0.77
Abril Educacao	2	1	0.38
Haelequin	5	3	1.15
Sanoma	7	8	3.07
OLMA Media Group	1	3	1.15

Using AHP, a pairwise comparison of the individual perspectives of the recommended publishers was carried out, and weights were allocated to the respective criteria. The consistency ratio (CR) and the consistency index (CI) of the matrix were determined to be 0.102 and 0.889, respectively for both criteria and sub-criteria. The pair-wise comparisons were made up of the elements of each hierarchy employing a ratio scale. Then, the comparisons were quantified to establish a comparison matrix, and the consistency index (CI) of the matrix was derived, which signifies the relative weights among the various elements of a defined hierarchy. The eigenvalue was used to assess the strength of the consistency ratio of the comparative matrix and determine whether or not to accept the information (Blagojevic et al., 2016). The results were sent as input to MLP-NN for optimisation, which outputs either a 'yes' for acceptance or a 'no' for retraining of the MLP-NN by adjusting the weight values to make a precise buying decision.

Four elicitation methods described by Kim and Park (2004), namely geometric mean eigenvector (EV), fuzzy preference programming (FPP), normalised column sum (NCS) and weighted least-square (WLS) were tested based on the respondents' perspectives. The levels of consistency of individual judgments were determined by measuring dissonance and congruence in the AHP analysis. The evaluation criterion comprised various judgments from both the publishers' library experts and the library team, which were later extended into a multi-layer structure. By weighting the various criteria according to the purchasing objectives as well as the alternatives, the final scores of the alternatives were determined.

4.7.1 AHP Analysis

This experiment used PriEsT to generate the AHP pairwise comparison matrix for visualising the level of inconsistency and the transitive judgement. The congruence and dissonance measurements in Figure 25 show the contribution of individual judgements to the overall inconsistency of the pairwise comparison matrix (PCM). These measurements are used later to detect and correct inconsistent judgements. In particular, Figure 25 visualises consistency and inconsistency among criteria showing the congruence and dissonance levels of individual judgement. The overall congruence and dissonance are $\psi = 0.083$ and $\Theta = 0.905$, respectively.

Figure 25: Visualizing level of Inconsistency with Congruence and Dissonance Levels

Figure 26 shows the following 8 criteria, namely, price (A), publisher (B), delivery (C), trust (D), title (E), publication period (F), discount (G) and author (H), which were compared on a ratio scale of 1-9, as discussed in Section 3. The result clearly shows the level of inconsistency for each individual judgement. Figure 26a shows connections between two nodes with a thick black line representing the dominant nodes. The preferences of publishers over trust and those of trust over discount suggest that a particular publisher would be preferred over discount. In Figure 26b, the triad for the comparison matrix (CM) among publishers, trust and discount is shown. The blue lines indicate a strong relationship among the publishers, discount and trust level. Figure 27 shows how the equaliser PCM captures the potential cause of priority violations. For instance, from Figure 27, trust was preferred by decision-makers over discount and all the other (indirect) judgements. In contrast, the discount was also preferred over the publication period, which was in contradiction to what other judgements have suggested. This is evidence of indirect judgement called latent violation.

Figure 26: Network view for Intransitive Set of Judgments (a) Depicts the Transitive Set of Individual Judgment. (b) Triad of CM on Publisher, Trust and Shipping.

Figure 27: Equalizer View for the PCM

We further evaluated the performance of AHP regarding geometric mean (GM), eigenvector (EV), normalised column sum (NCS), weighted least squares (WLS) and fuzzy preference programming (FPP). Table 17 shows the values for total deviation along with the number of violations and their corresponding second order deviations. The priority vectors were obtained using GM, EV, NCS, WLS, and FPP in Table 17. The set of weights (w) was used to analyse consistency in judgements with the highest weight in bold. The ideal possible ranking for the pairwise comparison matrix of the eight criteria given in Figure 27 is $A \rightarrow B \rightarrow C \rightarrow D \rightarrow E \rightarrow F \rightarrow G \rightarrow H$.

However, the ranking order suggested by GM, EV and NCS is $A \rightarrow H \rightarrow B \rightarrow D \rightarrow C \rightarrow E \rightarrow G \rightarrow F$. Though the judgments were found to be transitive, the WLS method violated the order of preference with $A \rightarrow H \rightarrow B \rightarrow D \rightarrow C \rightarrow G \rightarrow E \rightarrow F$ for one judgment; note the changed positions of E against G. The FPP result also suggests a different ranking order $A \rightarrow H \rightarrow B \rightarrow D \rightarrow C \rightarrow E \rightarrow G \rightarrow F$, with one violated judgment. Figure 28 shows the relationship between NV and TD, and that of TD and TD2. The results in Figure 28 reveal that decision-makers should be offered interactive selections for any non-dominated solutions, with GM lower than others, as shown in Figure 28(b). Any of the solutions with $NV > 0$ was considered to be inconsistent or less relevant. The FPP solution in Figure 28 revealed higher violations than GM, EV, NCS and WLS.

Table 17: Elicitation methods for the pairwise comparison matrix

Method	TD	NV	TD2	Vector							
				W ₁	W ₂	W ₃	W ₄	W ₅	W ₆	W ₇	W ₈
Geometric Mean (GM)	122.098	0	6248.061	0.284	0.16	0.065	0.128	0.042	0.022	0.035	0.264
Eigenvector (EV)	119.708	0	6354.109	0.266	0.165	0.065	0.138	0.044	0.022	0.036	0.264
Normalized Column Sum (NCS)	103.325	0	6866.591	0.266	0.157	0.069	0.139	0.049	0.024	0.041	0.256
Weighted Least Square (WLS)	120.223	1	6811.598	0.295	0.179	0.05	0.083	0.035	0.029	0.036	0.292
Fuzzy Preference Programming (FPP)	126.992	1	7322.363	0.275	0.208	0.045	0.083	0.045	0.032	0.037	0.275

Figure 28: Visualizing Solutions for Library in (a) NV-TD Plane, (b) TD-TD2 Plane

4.7.2 MLP-NN Evaluation

The output prediction from the AHP includes sets of publishers' alternatives, serving as inputs into the MLP-NN. Weight was given to each input for computation. To determine the momentum coefficient β , the following were set: hidden nodes were set at 3, the learning rate (η) was fixed at 0.1 and the mean square error (MSE) was 0.01. Then, different β with values of 0.4, 0.5, 0.6, 0.7, 0.8 and 0.9 were tested 50 times.

Figure 29 shows the result with spiral decision boundaries, based on individual library team member perspectives versus accuracy. The individual library team perspectives are represented by blue dots, and publisher perspectives are shown with yellow dots. The dots that fell on the red areas were considered to be invalid decisions, whereas those that fell on the green areas were considered valid. Figure 29(b) and Figure 29(c) show some invalid decisions at the top left side. However, Figure 29(d) indicates that when the library team perspective increased, the precise and accurate predicted publisher(s) emerged. The degree of accuracy was within the range (-0.5 to 0.5). When individual perspectives fell around 0.5, the level of accuracy was found to be higher.

Figure 29: MLP Decision-Making Boundary based on individual Library Team Perspectives and Accuracy at different levels (a) 400 (b) 800 (c) 1200 (d) 1600

Figure 30 presents the mean square error and shows the trend as the individual perspective increases to 1800. It was observed that the more significant the number of purchases, the better the flexibility of the publishers regarding discounts and other offers. At 1800 individual perspectives, the MSE was reduced tremendously and became more stable. This showed consistency at a higher degree. A steady movement between 1600 and 1800 showed that the higher the individual library team members' perspectives, the lower the MSE. This is reflected in the high accuracy of the analysed decision. The decision accuracy of the proposed model was compared to that of the fuzzy-AHP, BCP and FBDS methods, as shown in Table 18. The result shows that our proposed model had a higher accuracy of 97.8%. Thus, the proposed analytic-MLP showed a significant enhancement to the organisation's decision-making process. Moreover, the computational time of the proposed analytic-MLP is significantly lower than the compared one.

Figure 30: MSE on Individual Library Team Member

Table 18: Analysis of Decision Making Accuracy.

Model	Level of Accuracy (%)	Computational time (ms)
BCP	89.30	8.16
FBDS	94.61	11.47
Fuzzy-AHP	95.98	8.39
Proposed Analytic-MLP	97.80	7.35

4.8 DISCUSSION

4.8.1 B2B Customer Satisfaction and Retention

One critical success factor for customer satisfaction and retention in e-commerce is how the vendor handles its trust. Though the trust of customers represents accumulated knowledge about the past and present of the vendor, however, its assessment may affect the future of the vendor. In this study, four metrics namely: failures publication, customer-vendor interaction, website update and security, were used to assess the capability of vendors in satisfying and retaining its customers. At first, an interlinking relation was observed in Table 5 among the failures publication, customer-vendor interaction, website update, and security. The trust level was highly significant when the four metrics were high. From Table 6, a customer trust could be seen as a reflection of its vendor's concentration on the customers' well-being.

However, Figures 19 (a) and 19 (b) shows higher trust level when security is measured with the other three trust metrics, compared to when failures publication, customer-vendor interaction, and website update are plotted against each other. Positive significant acceptance of the proposed trust metrics was further shown in Table 6 using the statistical *t*-test method. This means that the vendors need to develop and foster customer trust by addressing its specific dimensions.

The proactive outreach ability of the customer-vendor interaction gives the vendor the true power to satisfy and retain customers. This implies that the higher the trust level in customer-vendor interaction response the better the chances of customer retention. Moreover, it was found that failure to update website design may pass wrong information

as to whether the security of the business is up-to-date or if the business is still active, as shown in Figure 16. In addition, positive response towards website update could significantly reduce customer switching costs. It was discovered that failure publication offers appealing and attractive feedback for organisations as it helps to improve their customer satisfaction and retention strategies.

The results in Table 5 also shows that under conditions of high competitive intensity, failure publication is more significant when compared to other metrics. Thus, in highly competitive e-commerce environments, the trust level would be more influenced by the failure publication. The reverse is true in low competitive intensity e-commerce environments, where average levels of failures publication are the norm. In such e-commerce environments, the U-shaped relationship is accentuated, such that failures publication is a strong determinant of trust level, compared to how reputation has been used in several literatures for trust level determinant.

Sugeno-FIS acts as an interpolating supervisor of multiple controllers for application to different operating conditions of the system due to the linear dependence of each rule on the input trust metrics. Sugeno-FIS supports the smooth interpolation of the gains that would be applied across the input trust metrics. Thus, Sugeno was regarded as a natural and efficient gain scheduler. ANFIS, on the other hand, accounted for the optimisation of the trust level result from Sugeno-FIS. Hence, guaranteeing the continuity of the output layer. In addition, Figure 20(a) shows that Sugeno is computationally efficient. The combination of the back-propagation algorithm with a least square method also allows the ANFIS to learn directly from the modelled data.

4.8.2 B2B Customer Relationship Management

One of the most important factors related to the success of B2B is how the organisation maintains its customer relationship. Ability to keep the repeat customer is a significant impact on the financial status of any organisation. However, the proposed model does not only help in maintaining the repeat customer but also to monitor the performance of the shop-and-go customer, to optimise such customer to repeat customer when necessary. It was observed that unit transaction date, invoice number, and quantity had a more significant influence on the classification of the customer.

Genetic-based data mining is easier to construct compared to SVM or k-means that require more skilled manipulation to ensure over-fitting does not occur. It is somehow hard to apply background domain knowledge using SVM, whereas it is easier to noticed over-fitting in GDM. SVM required a higher level of building skills than GDM model, which makes building an SVM model costlier. Although, SVM and k-means provide more accurate model compared to the C5.0 algorithm especially for complex problems. However, there is also the risk of finding sub-optimal solutions and over-fitting as mentioned earlier.

This shows that the implementation of CRM involved not only the marketing or information technology department alone, but require everyone within the business to be actively involved.

4.8.3 B2B Purchase Decision-Making

Unlike in business to consumer (B2C), where buying stands alone and primarily requires little or no follow-up, in B2B the buying decision is full of emotions and fear surrounding

who will accommodate the flexibility of the decision (Thatcher et al., 2006; Amelinckx et al., 2008; Wiersema, 2013; Gordini and Veglio, 2017). In addition, B2B buying may involve dozens of individuals with different backgrounds and incentives in the buying process (Lilien, 2016). Consequently, buying decisions at the organisational level are rendered complex due to the diversities of the decision-makers' judgements (Wind and Thomas, 2010; Karimi, 2013; Grewal et al., 2015), with attendant inconsistencies experienced in buyers' opinions.

One of the most critical factors related to the success of B2B is how the organisation makes its decision. Though B2B e-commerce represents a higher reflection of what happens in B2C, its peculiarity is based on the number of business units that are involved in the decision-making process. In this case, the uniqueness of individual publishers was first considered by each library team member, as shown in Figure 25, and individual differences in the choice of publishers by the library team members for each subject area were identified using cognitive reasoning, as shown in Figure 26. However, the publishers were not directly chosen but were chosen by their books.

Thus, the library organisation was considered to have features congruent with the individual team member's decision. The process described in this study allowed individuals to use a standard method in a variety of situations and adapt it to meet group situations, to satisfy the unique perspectives of individual members. The decisions made were effective since group decision-making allowed the selection of solutions that would both solve the problem and be acceptable to all individual group members. The findings of

this study suggest that the assessment of the BDM model using AHP, ANP and MLP-NN increases the consistency, flexibility and unity among organisation decision makers.

The AHP and ANP help an organisational buyer make simple decisions given complex options using multiple criteria selection, thereby overcoming inconsistencies in organisational decision making. The non-linear comparison of the AHP and ANP led to better results. MLP-NN, on the other hand, accounted for the optimisation of the predictive organisational measures. It dealt with the time complexity of the product alternative predictive process, thereby producing high-quality decision-making using optimal constraint satisfaction. Besides, forecasting errors were considerably reduced to the minimum level in comparison with those reported by Afef Denguir-Rekik (2009). This enables organisations to lower the cost of market participation, hence reducing transaction costs. The model facilitates flattening the organisational hierarchy, to improve its efficiency, lowering decision-making costs. Thus, the span of transaction control was also significantly reduced to the barest minimum. The model is also useful for keeping track of library inventory; hence flexibility on the part of the organisational buyer was increased. Risks and trade-offs among book quality, price, as well as discounts were avoided. Figures 27 and 28 show that creativity was initiated by making subjective rational decisions.

Figure 29 shows that both individual and supplier experts made decisions. The condensation of the two red and green colours represents the level of acceptance and rejection, respectively. Also, Figure 29 indicates a false acceptance of alternative products; even when the number of decision-makers increased, the MLP-NN was able to filter all low-rank alternatives, thereby improving the level of accuracy (see Figure 29(d)). This

clearly shows that an increase in decision-makers improved the level of accuracy in selecting the best product alternatives. Moreover, the increase in the number of publishers per book within a subject area (> 200), increased the number of computations and thus, cases of ambiguity could arise.

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

5.1 SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

5.1.1 B2B Trust Evaluation: Customer Satisfaction and Retention

The issue of trust becomes more exciting and somehow difficult to evaluate when it comes to customer satisfaction and retention. The conventional trust evaluation cannot analyse individual trust factors. The situation is often complicated and challenging in choosing the right metrics that would effectively predict the trust level of any vendor due to different customers' perspectives and beliefs. This has resulted in difficulty in customer satisfaction and retention. In this study, a novel model for vendor trust evaluation called Sugeno-ANFIS has been presented. Four trust metrics, which were considered for vendor trust evaluation are customer-vendor interaction, failure publication, website update and security.

The Sugeno-FIS maps the interpreted qualitative data as the trust input parameters to the input MF, and the input MF are mapped to rules. The rules are mapped to a set of output parameters while the output parameters are mapped to output MF, which later yielded a single-valued decision associated with the output. The ANFIS is used to tune the parameters of the Sugeno-FIS by optimising and validating the model using a checking data set to test for over-fitting of the training data. The proposed model was applied based on an examination of dedicated customers in e-commerce. Concerning the market environment, it was found that the metrics have positive statistical significance for customer satisfaction and retention. A crucial and exciting issue related to trust generation is the influence of failures publication. Our results showed that Failure publication has high

positive significance on trust generation compared to other three trust metrics. This is crucial because acknowledging inescapable facts constitute is a central attribute of transparent organisations. Indeed, clear evidence exists showing that a cover-up policy, once discovered, could lead to unbearable consequences, first for committing the error and secondly, for concealing or attempting to do so.

The proposed model has been tested by integrating it into an existing model of the organization, and the result proved promising with regards to switching costs by potential customers'. This signified that the model could be adapted to other types of e-commerce beside the three categories of e-commerce that were tested.

5.1.2 Customer Relationship Management

The B2B e-commerce CRM process is complicated and sometimes encounters problems of inconsistency due to a large number of people involved in the decision making. Previous research efforts based on data mining techniques, neural network, require optimisation at various stages such as feature selection or determining the optimal user-defined parameter to produce an accurate result. Thereby, reducing the computational speed, increasing computational time, and computational complexity. In this study, a novel model for CRM process using genetic-based data mining has been proposed. A typical construction company scenario was used as a case study. Transaction attributes were used. The C5.0 algorithm was used to generate the rules using the training set. Optimizing the rules using genetic algorithm elevate the level of accuracy and high computational speed was observed.

The model was able to enhance the CRM process by addressing some of the problems mentioned earlier and reduction in loss of customers to other competitors. The genetic data mining accounted for optimisation of the seller predictive measures. The algorithm was applied on B2B customers, and we can classify the B2B customer into a repeat customer and shop-and-go customer. Three rules with higher accuracy have been generated with this algorithm. In addition, the proposed model was computationally effective in ensuring high consistency in sellers' opinions, thereby improving the chances of not losing repeat customer that might cause financial breakdown of the entire business. The proposed model, therefore, provided a reliable CRM environment for easy deployment across multiple sellers, thereby maximising business performance.

The proposed model could find application in other B2B scenarios such as agriculture and publisher library. Human resources should be recognised as one of the vital keys to the success of CRM beside technology. Effective use of the system can win back any customers who are being lost to the competitive world.

5.1.3 Purchase Decision-Making

The B2B e-commerce decision-making process is complicated and often encounters problems with inconsistency due to the number of purchased units and the higher number of participating decision-makers. Previous research efforts based on AHP, for instance, were faced with ranking irregularities. In this work, a novel model of the B2B buying decision-making process using a combination of two multi-criteria decision-making methods, namely AHP and MLP-NN, has been presented. A typical library-publishers scenario was used as a case study. Book factors were used as the criteria and the publishers

as the alternatives. The AHP assigned weight to each book criterion using a pairwise comparison matrix with an arrangement based on priority. The consistency of the judgement levels was measured based on congruence and dissonance. The MLP-NN was used to develop specific non-linear mapping by adjusting the network weights using a learning algorithm. The combination fostered cognitive reasoning for decision filtering by scanning through the multiple-criteria of book publishers.

The model enhanced the decision-making process by addressing the challenge of the occurrence of ranking irregularities encountered in AHP. The MLP-NN accounted for optimisation of the predictive organisational measures. In addition, the proposed technique was computationally effective in ensuring high consistency in buyers' opinions, thereby improving the choice of the indexes that conformed to the common agreements of the buyers. This indicates that the intensity of the process, regarding the number of alternatives and criteria, were dependent on both decision-making and knowledge acquisition. The proposed model, therefore, provided a reliable decision-making environment for easy deployment of sales efforts across multiple publishers, thereby maximising organisation buyers' performance.

In comparison with AHP, ELECTRE and PROMETHEE, which only ranked alternatives and calculated the weights of attributes for service evaluation, the addition of proposed MLP-NN enhanced knowledge acquisition, resolved conflicts of ideas and fostered cognitive reasoning through decision filtering. Moreover, MLP-NN was capable of deploying sales efforts based on multiple criteria to maximise buyers' performance.

The proposed model could find applications in other B2B scenarios such as agriculture and the food (agri-food) sector. In this case, due to the increasing growth in market demand for food, particularly perishable produce, new primary producers and marketers are seeking out on a regular basis; and deciding to purchase and market some agricultural produce would depend on some factors. Thus, the model could be used to tackle the problem of post-harvest losses of primary producers.

5.2 CONTRIBUTIONS TO KNOWLEDGE

The proposed HyperTernary model improves the consistency of customers and vendors by resolving decision conflicts within a short period. The proposed model fosters cognitive reasoning through decisions' filtering and the ability to deploy sales efforts across multiple criteria in order to maximise buyers' performances. Hence, customer satisfaction and retention would be achieved. The decision makers interactively explore and revise their judgments based on the congruence and dissonance measures. The trust of vendors assists customers' decision in order to deploy their buying strategies and readily prepare for accurate decisions when confronted with unpredictable buying decisions.

5.3 LIMITATIONS

It was observed in the Analytic-MLP, that when the number of decisions-making exceeded some limits, some level of inconsistencies could also set in. In addition, high computational time was observed in the Sugeno-ANFIS as a result of the Gaussian membership function used in order to achieve high accuracy in customer satisfaction and retention.

5.4 RECOMMENDATION FOR FUTURE WORK

A possible direction for future work could be to find some other methods to calculate the relative importance of criteria, instead of assigning weighted coefficient values for the importance of criteria based on decision-makers' experiences to improve on decision accuracy. The model could be used to tackle the problem of post-harvest losses of primary producers. A Lightweight Dual Gateway Protocol can be used to secure customer payment.

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APPENDICES

A. HyperTernary Code

Helper.py

```
import boto.ses
import sendgrid
import requests
import mandrill
from django.core.mail import EmailMultiAlternatives
from django.conf import settings

def send_mail(mto, mfrom, msubject, mbody, user_active):
    if mfrom:
        mfrom = mfrom
    else:
        mfrom = settings.DEFAULT_FROM_EMAIL
    if user_active:
        mail_sender = settings.MAIL_SENDER
    else:
        mail_sender = settings.INACTIVE_MAIL_SENDER
    if mail_sender == 'AMAZON':
        # conn=SESConnection(settings.AM_ACCESS_KEY,
settings.AM_PASS_KEY)
        conn = boto.ses.connect_to_region(
            settings.AWS_REGION,
            aws_access_key_id=settings.AM_ACCESS_KEY,
            aws_secret_access_key=settings.AM_PASS_KEY
        )
        response = conn.send_email(mfrom, msubject, mbody, mto, format='html')
    elif mail_sender == 'MAILGUN':
        response = requests.post(
            settings.MGUN_API_URL,
            auth=('api', settings.MGUN_API_KEY),
            data={
                'from': mfrom,
                'to': mto,
```

```

        'subject': msubject,
        'html': mbody,
    })
elif mail_sender == 'SENDGRID':
    sg = sendgrid.SendGridClient(settings.SG_USER, settings.SG_PWD)
    sending_msg = sendgrid.Mail()
    sending_msg.set_subject(msubject)
    sending_msg.set_html(mbody)
    sending_msg.set_text(msubject)
    sending_msg.set_from(mfrom)
    sending_msg.add_to(mto)
    response = sg.send(sending_msg)
elif mail_sender == 'MANDRILL':
    api_key = settings.MANDRILL_API_KEY
    mandrill_client = mandrill.Mandrill(api_key)

    message = {
        "html": mbody,
        "subject": msubject,
        "from_email": mfrom,
        "from_name": "Django CRM",
        "to": [{ 'email': i, 'type': 'to' } for i in mto]
    }
    response = mandrill_client.messages.send(message=message)

else:
    msg = EmailMultiAlternatives(msubject, mbody, mfrom, [mto])
    msg.attach_alternative(mbody, "text/html")
    response = msg.send()
return response

```

Settings.py

```
import os
```

```
# Build paths inside the project like this: os.path.join(BASE_DIR, ...)
```

```
BASE_DIR = os.path.dirname(os.path.dirname(os.path.abspath(__file__)))
```

```
# SECURITY WARNING: keep the secret key used in production secret!
SECRET_KEY = 'mwx@&97%!$fx_*zgj(2ygi^(s=oh5j(cqb$=+-mkd9scbt!0v0'
# SECURITY WARNING: don't run with debug turned on in production!
DEBUG = False
ALLOWED_HOSTS = ['*']
# Application definition
LOGIN_REDIRECT_URL = '/'
LOGIN_URL = '/login/'
INSTALLED_APPS = [
    'django.contrib.auth',
    'django.contrib.contenttypes',
    'django.contrib.messages',
    'django.contrib.sessions',
    'django.contrib.staticfiles',
    'simple_pagination',
    'compressor',
    'common',
    'accounts',
    'cases',
    'contacts',
    'emails',
    'leads',
    'opportunity',
    'planner',
    'sorl.thumbnail',
]
```

```

MIDDLEWARE = [
    'django.middleware.security.SecurityMiddleware',
    'django.middleware.common.CommonMiddleware',
    'django.contrib.sessions.middleware.SessionMiddleware',
    'django.contrib.auth.middleware.AuthenticationMiddleware',
    'django.contrib.messages.middleware.MessageMiddleware',
    'django.middleware.clickjacking.XFrameOptionsMiddleware',
]

ROOT_URLCONF = 'crm.urls'

TEMPLATES = [
    {
        'BACKEND': 'django.template.backends.django.DjangoTemplates',
        'DIRS': [os.path.join(BASE_DIR, "templates"), ],
        'APP_DIRS': True,
        'OPTIONS': {
            'context_processors': [
                'django.template.context_processors.debug',
                'django.template.context_processors.request',
                'django.contrib.auth.context_processors.auth',
                'django.contrib.messages.context_processors.messages',
            ],
        },
    },
]

WSGI_APPLICATION = 'crm.wsgi.application'

# Database

# https://docs.djangoproject.com/en/1.10/ref/settings/#databases

```

```

DATABASES = {
    'default': {
        'ENGINE': 'django.db.backends.postgresql',
        'NAME': 'dj_crm',
        'USER': 'postgres',
        'PASSWORD': 'root',
        'HOST': '127.0.0.1',
        'PORT': '5432'
    }
}

STATICFILES_DIRS = [os.path.join(BASE_DIR, "static"), ]

# Password validation
# https://docs.djangoproject.com/en/1.10/ref/settings/#auth-password-validators

AUTH_PASSWORD_VALIDATORS = [
    {
        'NAME':
'django.contrib.auth.password_validation.UserAttributeSimilarityValidator',
    },
    {
        'NAME': 'django.contrib.auth.password_validation.MinimumLengthValidator',
    },
    {
        'NAME': 'django.contrib.auth.password_validation.CommonPasswordValidator',
    },
    {
        'NAME': 'django.contrib.auth.password_validation.NumericPasswordValidator',
    },
]

```

```
# Internationalization

# https://docs.djangoproject.com/en/1.10/topics/i18n/

LANGUAGE_CODE = 'en-us'
TIME_ZONE = 'Asia/Calcutta'
USE_I18N = True
USE_L10N = True
USE_TZ = True

# Static files (CSS, JavaScript, Images)
# https://docs.djangoproject.com/en/1.10/howto/static-files/
STATIC_URL = '/static/'

EMAIL_BACKEND = 'django.core.mail.backends.smtp.EmailBackend'
# EMAIL_BACKEND = 'django.core.mail.backends.dummy.EmailBackend'

# EMAIL_HOST = 'localhost'
# EMAIL_PORT = 25

# AUTHENTICATION_BACKENDS = ('django.contrib.auth.backends.ModelBackend',
)

EMAIL_HOST = 'smtp.sendgrid.net'
EMAIL_HOST_USER = os.getenv('SG_USER', '')
EMAIL_HOST_PASSWORD = os.getenv('SG_PWD', '')
EMAIL_PORT = 587
EMAIL_USE_TLS = True

MEDIA_ROOT = os.path.join(BASE_DIR, 'media')
MEDIA_URL = '/media/'
AUTH_USER_MODEL = 'common.User'

STATIC_URL = '/static/'
```

```
STATICFILES_DIRS = (BASE_DIR + '/static',)
STATICFILES_FINDERS = (
    'django.contrib.staticfiles.finders.FileSystemFinder',
    'django.contrib.staticfiles.finders.AppDirectoriesFinder',
    'compressor.finders.CompressorFinder',
)

COMPRESS_ROOT = BASE_DIR + '/static/'
COMPRESS_URL = STATIC_URL
COMPRESS_ENABLED = True

COMPRESS_CSS_FILTERS = ['compressor.filters.css_default.CssAbsoluteFilter',
    'compressor.filters.cssmin.CSSMinFilter']
COMPRESS_REBUILD_TIMEOUT = 5400

COMPRESS_OUTPUT_DIR = 'CACHE'
COMPRESS_URL = STATIC_URL
COMPRESS_ENABLED = True

COMPRESS_PRECOMPILERS = (
    ('text/less', 'lessc {infile} {outfile}'),
    ('text/x-sass', 'sass {infile} {outfile}'),
    ('text/x-scss', 'sass --scss {infile} {outfile}'),
)

COMPRESS_OFFLINE_CONTEXT = {
    'STATIC_URL': 'STATIC_URL',
}
```

```
DEFAULT_FROM_EMAIL = 'no-reply@django-crm.micropyramid.com'
```

```
MAIL_SENDER = 'AMAZON'
```

```
INACTIVE_MAIL_SENDER = 'MANDRILL'
```

```
AM_ACCESS_KEY = os.getenv('AM_ACCESS_KEY', "")
```

```
AM_PASS_KEY = os.getenv('AM_PASS_KEY', "")
```

```
AWS_REGION = os.getenv('AWS_REGION', "")
```

```
MGUN_API_URL = os.getenv('MGUN_API_URL', "")
```

```
MGUN_API_KEY = os.getenv('MGUN_API_KEY', "")
```

```
SG_USER = os.getenv('SG_USER', "")
```

```
SG_PWD = os.getenv('SG_PWD', "")
```

```
MANDRILL_API_KEY = os.getenv('MANDRILL_API_KEY', "")
```

```
ADMIN_EMAIL = "admin@micropyramid.com"
```

```
try:
```

```
    from .dev_settings import *
```

```
except ImportError:
```

```
    pass
```

```
HyperTernaryTemplate.py
```

```
{% extends 'base.html' %}
```

```
{% load staticfiles %}
```

```
{% load thumbnail %}
```

```
{% block content% }
```

```
<!-- OPPORTUNITY VIEW STARTS -->
```

```
<div class="main_container" id="maincontainer">
```

```
<div class="overview_form_block row marl justify-content-center">
```

```
<div class="col-md-6">
```

```
<div class="card">
```

```
<div class="card-body" id="datashow">
```

```
<div class="panel-heading card-title view-pad text-center">
```

```
<h5>
```

```
Profile
```

```
<!-- <span class="float-right" style="margin-top: 0px">
```

```
<div class="dropdown buttons_row">
```

```
<button class="btn btn-primary dropdown-toggle save" type="button" data-  
toggle="dropdown">Actions
```

```
<span class="caret"></span></button>
```

```
<ul class="dropdown-menu">
```

```
<li><a href="#" >Edit</a></li>
```

```
<li class="delete_contact"><a href="#"  
id="remove_contact">Remove</a></li>
```

```
</ul>
```

```
</div>
```

```
</span> -->
```

```
</h5>
```

```
<a href="{% url 'common:edit_user' user_obj.id %}" class="btn btn-success  
edit">Edit</a>
```

```
</div>
```

```
<div class="row marl no-gutters">
```

```
<div class="col-md-8">
```

```

    {% if user_obj.first_name %}
    <div class="filter_col col-md-12">
        <div class="form-group">
            <label class="contact_field_label" for="id_name" data-
name="name">Name</label>
            <div class="contact_field" id="contact_name" data-name="name">{{
user_obj.first_name }} {{ user_obj.last_name }}</div>
        </div>
    </div>
    {% endif %}
    <div class="filter_col col-md-12">
        <div class="form-group">
            <label class="contact_field_label" for="id_contact_account" data-
name="name">UserName</label>
            <div class="contact_field" id="contact_account" data-name="name">{{
user_obj.username }}</div>
        </div>
    </div>
    <div class="filter_col col-md-12">
        <div class="form-group">
            <label class="contact_field_label" for="id_email" data-
name="name">Email</label>
            <div class="contact_field" id="contact_email" data-name="name">{{
user_obj.email }}</div>
        </div>
    </div>
    <div class="col-md-4">
        <div class="profile_pic">
            {% if user_obj.profile_pic %}

```

```
        {% thumbnail request.user.profile_pic "125x125" as im %}
        
        {% endthumbnail %}
    {% else %}
        
        {% endif %}
    </div>
<!-- OPPORTUNITY VIEW ENDS -->
{% endblock %}
```